

MAELSTROM

Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable
RemOval and Management

D9.4

Second Interim Communication and Dissemination Report

22.12.2023

General Information

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1 Executive Summary

The present document refers to the Second Interim Communication and Dissemination Report of the EU-funded project MAELSTROM – Smart technology for MArinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management.

The document is deliverable 9.4 of Work Package 9 and intends to inform the European Commission and the MAELSTROM consortium of the communication and dissemination activities implemented by the consortium during the first 36 months of project's activity.

Although communication and dissemination activities are fully complementary, they have been reported as two separate chapters: we will be referring to **communication** when reporting past and ongoing efforts to create opportunities for promoting the MAELSTROM project, its relevance, and milestones to a multitude of audiences - including the media and the public; we will be referring to **dissemination** when reporting past and ongoing efforts to promote and facilitate the use of MAELSTROM's research and technological results among potential users, beneficiaries and peers within the fields of research, industry, commerce and policymaking.

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2 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM - *Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management* is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020, pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question of the removal and sustainable treatment of the marine litter legacy; it contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with fully-fledged circular economy and society-oriented solutions. In particular, the project:

- (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas.
- (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable, and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second-generation fuel, to identify, remove, and sort marine litter.
- (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems.
- (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation.
- (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of MAELSTROM solutions, also providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products.
- (vi) enhances social awareness on the issue of marine litter and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities.
- (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

3 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following partners.

Table 1 - MAELSTROM partners

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	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.gouttefarde@lirmm.fr

4 Aim of the Deliverable

The present document refers to the Second Interim Communication and Dissemination Report of the EU-funded project MAELSTROM. The document is Deliverable 9.4 of Work Package 9 and provides an overview of the main activities and actions related to communication and dissemination efforts put in place during the first 36 months of the project.

The basis of this document is D.9.2. "*Final Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination*" delivered in December 2022, which has set a Consortium's agreed strategy, common rules and work plan for the communication and dissemination activities of the MAELSTROM project.

The document provides an overview of the participation and representation of the MAELSTROM project at physical and online events, relevant publications, networking actions and an overview of web and social media performances; it illustrates the efforts made by the Consortium in the last 36 months to translate MAELSTROM's mission and achievements into engagement opportunities for the international community, local stakeholders and civil society, mainly in Vila do Conde, (Portugal) and Venice (Italy), the pilot locations where the project's technologies were implemented. Moreover, the document reports the alignment of the project with the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters", alongside goals of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda.

5 Work Package Description

The scope of Work Package 9 (WP9): *Dissemination and Communication* - is to create strategic opportunities for promoting MAELSTROM's outcomes to a multitude of audiences. Those include potential users and peers within the fields of research, industry, commercial and policymaking, while also engaging the civil society, the media, and the public. Activities under Work Package 9 are formally led by CIMA Research Foundation and supported by the MAELSTROM's consortium, composed of 14 partners from 8 European countries. Partners range from excellence research centres in the fields of marine life, biology, sustainable energy, artificial intelligence and robotics to private multinational and national recycling companies with certified industrial plants. Other partners include a market consultancy company, a micro-

enterprise and a marine-litter and plastics orientated NGO. The combination of such different backgrounds and areas of expertise is a strategic asset for MAELSTROM's dissemination and communication efforts. The Work Package 9 includes five main tasks as illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1 - Communication and Dissemination Tasks

Task 9.1. - Communication and Dissemination Plans

Task 9.2. - Project Branding & Media

Task 9.3. - Support Capacity Building Actions

Task 9.4. - Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes (linked with WP7)

Task 9.5. - Support Project's events

Despite having chosen to structure the dissemination and communication efforts in two separated chapters, both converge and complement each other to achieve common goals, namely:

1. To increase the **success and reputation** of the MAELSTROM project, highlighting the consortium's identity, efforts, skills, innovations, and project-related initiatives.
2. To draw the attention of multiple stakeholders and audiences regarding **marine litter impacts** on ecosystems and on the existing solutions to mitigate them.

3. To demonstrate the way **MAELSTROM's outcomes can become relevant to our everyday lives**, by introducing novel technologies and improving lives through environmental regeneration, the creation of new market's segments and associated jobs within a circular economy paradigm.
4. To create **market demand** for marine litter removal technologies and recycled products by fostering awareness on marine litter impacts, promoting innovative solutions for litter removal, and highlighting the advantages of recycled products for the industrial supply chain.
5. To develop and deliver **economic feasibility** studies regarding the adoption, functioning and maintenance of MAELSTROM's removal technologies.
6. To make good use of findings, by assuring they are taken up by decision-makers in **policymaking**, as well as by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up. As part of the efforts to achieve this goal, MAELSTROM has delivered a *Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter* (month 12) as part of Work Package 7. The document is the result of a consultation process among international stakeholders regarding the gaps and opportunities on communication and dissemination efforts in marine litter-related activities. The overarching goal of the document is to contribute towards improved policies and legislations regarding marine litter knowledge within the European space. The document can be consulted at the EC Cordis website at the following link <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5eea84531&appId=PPGMS>
7. To demonstrate how the European collaboration has produced **scientific excellence**, contributing to solve the societal challenge posed by marine litter on living ecosystems.

6 General update

Since the *First Interim Communication and Dissemination Report*, delivered in June 2022, the main highlight for the MAELSTROM project in the last eighteen months was the fact that both marine litter removal technologies proposed by the project have been implemented and officially launched.

The well-functioning of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform (Venice, Italy) and of the Bubble Barrier (Vila do Conde, Portugal), alongside the commitment and engagement of local authorities on both locations has reached unexpected levels of success, which the Consortium interpreted as the result of fruitful stakeholder engagement processes and a sign of potentially increased sustainability.

To support such achievements, MAELSTROM's communication and dissemination efforts have diversified in two different ways:

i) by continuing the previous efforts to gain visibility within the international community, positioning itself as a relevant EU-funded project which, through science and technology, contributes to address the issue of marine litter and plastic pollution; ii) by supporting the Consortium's partners in charge of the stakeholder engagement processes (CIIMAR, CNR, VLPF), through the provision of quality information on MAELSTROM's mission and technologies. These efforts were put in place through multiple channels and tools - from traditional to digital media - based on the specific needs of each context and partner.

As an endorser of the EU Mission Charter "Restore our Ocean and Waters" and through its own organized events, MAELSTROM has reached out to other EU-funded projects and initiatives alike, promoting an open collaboration towards the implementation of the EU Mission as well as other international frameworks such as the 2030 Agenda and the UN Ocean Decade.

A significant number of invitations to participate at public and technical events, as well as requests for networking and collaborations were observed and have been fully embraced by the Consortium. In September 2023, MAELSTROM has been highlighted in the European Research Council Executive Agency factsheet as a project contributing to the EU Mission; in October 2023, MAELSTROM was awarded the All-Atlantic Project Award under the category *Healthy Oceans and Resilient Coasts*.

The positive results of the communication and dissemination work package are also possible due to the significant number of public events promoted by the project and implemented by several partners in Italy and Portugal: conferences, workshops, beach clean-ups and info sessions at schools have often translated into a manifested interest and support to the project by the people involved. As a result, MAELSTROM's presence on social media has grown and received attention from several European Offices, such as the European Research Council Executive Agency, Cordis and the European Commission's Science and Innovation Program (H2020); this was followed by an increase in the number of followers and the number of interactions with MAELSTROM's info email and social media channels, which is gradually building-up a digital community that follows the project attentively, supporting its activities and disseminating it on their own channels.

As part of the Consortium's commitment to the marine litter challenge, future efforts will keep exploring traditional and social media to describe the efficiency of MAELSTROM's technologies in removing and identifying marine litter, their environmental impacts and the effective recycling possibilities and exploitation strategies. This will be based on a clear and accessible communication and dissemination approach - one that creates a multilevel understanding, engagement and commitment regarding plastic pollution and marine litter.

7 Communication strategy: update for M36

The communication strategy adopted for the MAELSTROM project was designed to follow the project's evolution, to engage all partners in the communication efforts and to easily adapt to unforeseen situations (e.g., delays in activities, third parties' involvement, and requests for visibility, etc.).

During the first two and a half years - while waiting for the implementation of the marine litter removal technologies to be installed - communication efforts focused primarily on promoting MAELSTROM's **identity and purpose/mission** to a vast international community: target audiences included scientific, technological, industrial, investors, donors, civil society, and policy makers (for further details please see *Deliverable 9.2: Final Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination*). This was done through a tailored content creation activity, later applied to a communication kit comprising a project website, informative multimedia materials and social media profiles.

From an early stage, communicative links were established among MAELSTROM's activities and the goals of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, the Sustainable Development Goals and more recently with the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" program of action. The aim with this exercise is to both support and give visibility to the existing international frameworks on marine litter, plastic pollution, and circular economy but also to position the MAELSTROM project within those frameworks, showing how the project is concretely contributing to their implementation, through the activities deployed.

Although the communication coordinator - CIMA Research Foundation - bears leadership of communication activities, all partners pro-actively support the communication efforts: strong linkages with partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, leading the communication aspects of the In-No-Plastic project and with a vast experience on public awareness/beach clean-ups events in the Venice area, have proved very fruitful and will continue throughout the project duration. Due to the complementary among WP7 and WP9, the partner CIIMAR from Portugal has been extremely supportive by engaging local stakeholders and co-organizing public events which brought wide visibility to the project (e.g., Vilo do Conde Sunset Beach Clean-up, All Atlantic Award, launch event of the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde). On the other side, the communication team has supported CIIMAR on the international stakeholder mapping and will keep collaborating with CIIMAR for the 2024 events

(namely: Beach clean-up in September 2024 and Final project event in November/December 2024).

MAELSTROM's editorial initiative MAELDrops - graphically illustrated scientific facts, published on social media on average once every 2 months - have now been enriched by MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews regarding specific partner's activities developed within the project. The aim is to highlight single partners activities, so to *valorise* their scientific, *technological*, and social backgrounds and the impacts brought to the MAELSTROM project.

Regarding present and planned communication efforts, those will focus on promoting the exploitation strategy - presently being developed by partner Alpha - while maintaining stakeholders' and citizen's engagement and interest on the MAELSTROM's technologies and topics. Efforts will also be done to communicate and facilitate the comprehension of the results of the undergoing environmental monitoring campaigns and recycling opportunities in the Ave River and in the Venice Lagoon.

Figure 2 - Communication efforts through the years

7.1 Media & Branding | Task 9.2

7.1.1 Logo

MAELSTROM's logo has suffered no changes since the beginning of the project. Through its lines, shapes, and colours, it represents some of the natural elements and settings related to the project's implementation and activities. The logo was studied to perform well in multiple formats, from traditional printing to T-shirts, web media, apps, and gadgets.

Figure 3 - MAELSTROM Logo visual elements

7.1.2 Events Kit

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

Due to the number of events foreseen by the project and the ones to which the consortium members were/are/will be invited to attend, the communication team has set an Events Kit. The kit was designed in the first months of the project suiting formal (e.g., conferences) and informal events (such as clean-ups): it includes internal and external roll-ups, brochures, flags, T-shirts, bags and document/ppt templates. The Events Kit is openly available to the consortium's partners through the dedicated MS Teams channel, the SeedsDMS repository and on the MAELSTROM website, under the media kit section (link above).

Printing of materials is reduced to the necessary minimum quantities due to its environmental impact and is done when no other (digital) alternatives are available or suitable, in which cases eco-printing is strongly encouraged.

A trilingual brochure - English, Italian, and Portuguese - was developed in 2023 with in-depth details regarding the project's aims, technologies, and events. The brochure has proven to be very effective as the three languages fully represent the consortium and the two pilot areas where MAELSTROM's technologies are implemented and where local stakeholder involvement is of utmost importance.

For the Launch Event of the Bubble Barrier in Portugal, held on November 25th 2023, a small number of pins were produced and distributed among the Consortium as a way to identify the team among the vast audience attending the event.

Figure 4 – Portuguese prime minister Antonio Costa (center), Paulo Jorge Ferreira, Rector of the Universidade de Aveiro (left) and Luis Vieira, researcher from MAELSTROM partner CIIMAR (right) during the Ciência Viva event, Portugal, July 2023

7.1.3 Videos

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwGpE7VUFUsoiKdgFuZUvUQ>

Five videos illustrating different MAELSTROM products have been developed as part of the communication strategy: a [first video describing the project](#) was produced in 2021 and projected during *the 1st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy*, held in Venice during the International Boat Show. The video used an infographic approach as no "real" footage in the project existed yet and it aimed at providing an overall view of the MAELSTROM's mission and goals. Since then, four other videos were produced:

- i) a video illustrating the functioning of the [MAELSTROM app](#), in 2022.
- ii) a teaser video announcing the implementation of a [Bubble Barrier](#) in the Ave River, in Vila do Conde, Portugal, which was projected during the *UN Ocean Conference* held in June 2022, in Lisbon.
- iii) a video describing the design, production and functioning of the [Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform](#) in the Venice Lagoon, in 2023.
- iv) a video illustrating the **Launch Event of the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde** which describes the implementation process of the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River, highlighting the work of the consortium's partners directly involved in the process, as well as the role of key stakeholders for the successful implementation of the technology in Vila do Conde (in revision, yet to be published).

Studies are presently being made to check the economic feasibility of having a dedicated video on the recycling processes being developed by our team, as well as a last conclusive video with MAELSTROM's highlights to be presented during the final conference in 2024. To produce MAELSTROM's videos, local video companies have been contracted both in Italy and in Portugal and worked under the guidance of the communication team. All the videos are uploaded on the dedicated section of the MAELSTROM's website and on MAELSTROM's You Tube channel (link above).

7.1.4 Newsletters

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/>

Biannual newsletters are delivered in June and December to the MAELSTROM consortium and to subscribers through a dedicated Mail Chimp service. Newsletters

consist of a summary of main project's activities and milestones. In total, five newsletters were sent since 2021 and, as we write, a sixth newsletter is being prepared to be sent on the week 18-22 of December 2023. A repository of all the newsletters is available in a dedicated section on the MAELSTROM's website (see link above). Subscription to MAELSTROM's newsletter is done by filling the dedicated form on the project's website (homepage). Data protection regarding the subscription is in accordance with the 2018 GDPR.

In addition to the biannual newsletters the communication team uses the Mail Chimp service to share invitations to relevant events (e.g., Launch Event, All Atlantic Award). Annex 4 contains all the newsletters published by the MAELSTROM project.

7.1.5 Website

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/>

- 8100 views
- 2900 news users
- 1 minute 04 seconds average session time

Analysis period: January 2023 – 4th December 2023

Alongside social media channels, MAELSTROM's website is one of the main sources of information regarding MAELSTROM's main activities and milestones. In 2023 the website reached a total of 8.100 views of which 2.900 were from new users. Peaks in visits are observed when relevant events are posted, e.g.: Launch Event of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform on June 9th, Sunset Clean-up Vila do Conde on September 16th, Launch Event of the Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, on November 25th.

Figure 5 - MAELSTROM website: number of visits in the period January-December 2023

Figure 6 - MAELSTROM website: number of new visitors and returning visitors in the period January-December 2023

Users come mainly from Italy, Portugal, and the United States and, to a lesser extent, from France, The Netherlands, Spain, and Belgium. Most of the new users have visited the MAELSTROM website through a direct search (without using search engines). As for the organic traffic - through search engines - keywords mostly used to find the MAELSTROM website were "maelstrom project", "maelstrom", "project maelstrom" "maelstrom h2020".

The most viewed website pages are the *Home* page, the *About* page and the *Outputs* page, with an overall average engagement time of 1 minute and 04 seconds.

Figure 7 – MAELSTROM website: Users by country and user default channel group

Figure 8 - MAELSTROM website: views by page and user activity over time

7.1.6 Social media

MAELSTROM's social media profiles on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and have proved to be good opportunities for reaching multiple audiences and engaging them with the project's communication and dissemination goals. MAELSTROM's social media profiles have two main goals: i) to disseminate MAELSTROM's scientific and technological outcomes; ii) to foster citizen awareness on marine litter, plastic pollution, and circular economy possibilities.

Although MAELSTROM's digital community is limited (average 300 followers) it has presented a positive trend when compared to 2022. Page visits have increased by 125,4% on Facebook and 27% on Instagram when compared to 2022. Posts coverage has also increased by 9,8% on Facebook and 35,6% on Instagram, translated by 35 new followers in Facebook and 113 new followers in Instagram.

Facebook and Instagram

Figure 9 – MAELSTROM's Facebook and Instagram page visits and coverage in the period January-15 December 2023 when compared with Jan-Dec 2022

Facebook and Instagram users come mainly from Italy (Venice Region) and Portugal (Porto Region) and to a less extent from Spain, France, and Germany. Women represent 58,7% of the total followers in Facebook and 67,1% of users in Instagram. Followers' age is mostly representative on the range 25-54 years old

Figure 10 – MAELSTROM's Facebook and Instagram gender and age analysis

Figure 11 – MAELSTROM's Facebook and Instagram users' country

X (previously Twitter)

MAELSTROM's X (ex. Twitter) account counts with 233 followers when compared with 120 from 2022. Posts have reached 6.5K impressions over a 91-day period. Top tweets in 2023 correspond to the Demonstration Event of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning

Platform on the World environment Day and MAELSTROM’s participation at the event “2013-2023: 10 years of the Galway Statement”.

Figure 12 – MAELSTROM’s Twitter impressions and visits, 91-day summary (on 15/12/2023)

Figure 13 – Top 2023 tweets on MAELSTROM’s Twitter profile

LinkedIn

In line with the positive trend of the other social media channels, MAELSTROM's LinkedIn account has seen a significant increase in followers: from 146 followers in July 2022 to 372 followers in December 2023. The page has received a total of 1,074 visits over a one-year period (14/12/2022-13/12/2023) and 402 unique visitors. Followers come mainly from Portugal (Porto and Lisbon Metropolitan Areas), The Netherlands and to a lesser extent from Spain, Italy, and Denmark. 585 of MAELSTROM's LinkedIn followers have a job function related with Research, followed by Business Development, Project Management, Engineering and Education. Main industries represented by MAELSTROM followers are Research Services (22,8%), Higher Education (8,1%), Environmental Services (7,3%), Industrial Machinery Manufacturing (5,1%), Government Administrations (4%) and Non-profits Organizations (3,5%).

Figure 14 - MAELSTROM's LinkedIn follower metrics: page views, unique visitors, and number of total and new followers

Highlights

Data for 12/14/2022 - 12/13/2023

1,384
Reactions

27
Comments

105
Reposts

Metrics

Impressions ▾

✓ Organic

35,755

✓ Sponsored

0

Follower demographics

Location ▾

Porto Metropolitan Area, Portugal - 45 (12.1%)

Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal - 14 (3.8%)

The Randstad, Netherlands, Netherlands - 13 (3.5%)

Greater Bilbao Metropolitan Area, Spain - 9 (2.4%)

Greater Milan Metropolitan Area, Italy - 8 (2.2%)

Greater Genoa Metropolitan Area, Italy - 7 (1.9%)

Greater San Sebastian Area, Spain - 7 (1.9%)

Greater Aarhus Area, Denmark - 6 (1.6%)

Greater Venice Metropolitan Area, Italy - 6 (1.8%)

Greater Savona Metropolitan Area, Italy - 5 (1.3%)

Figure 15 - MAELSTROM's LinkedIn followers' metrics: impressions and location

Follower demographics

Job function

Follower demographics

Industry

Figure 16 - MAELSTROM's LinkedIn followers' metrics: job function and industry

7.1.7 MAELDrops

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maeldrops/>

Aiming at making topics on marine litter, plastic pollution, circular economy, and recycling innovations more accessible, the communication team developed an editorial project called MAELDrops - graphically illustrated postcards with scientific information, published on social media on average once every 2 months.

Sources of information to create the MAELDrops' contents come from scientific papers, reports by the EU, UN and accredited websites. The aim of this editorial initiative, not initially foreseen in the project proposal, is to translate scientific-based data into accessible information for the public in general. Since the beginning of the project, nineteen MAELDrops have been designed and published both on the MAELSTROM website and on the social media channels. A MAELDrops' repository is accessible at a dedicated section of the MAELSTROM's website (see link above). For reporting purposes. Annex 2 contains all the published MAELDrops.

Figure 17 - MAELDROP n. 19 – Plastic pollution is also an environmental justice issue.

7.1.8 Flash Interviews

After the editorial project regarding the above mentioned MAELDrops a new editorial project was brought to live in 2023: MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews. As the name suggests, these are short interviews (Q&A) with an average of four questions each and around 300 words per answer. Interviews are done to consortium's partners and regard their specific role and activities developed within the MAELSTROM project. The aim is to highlight single partners activities, to *valorise* their scientific, *technological*, and social backgrounds as well as the impacts brought to the project through their contributions. To date *five* Q&A Flash Interviews have been published *and during 2024 we intend to cover the remaining partners*. Annex 3 contains all the published Q&A Flash Interviews.

Figure 18 - MAELSTROM Flash Interview n. 1 - Talking about robotics and sustainability with Damien Sallé (Tecnalia)

7.1.9 Recycled Plastic Whales

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstrom-outputs/>

Three real-sized plastic sperm whale installations were created with recycled plastic provided by the Ecopolietilene consortium (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>) with whom the project has established an MoU.

The reason for choosing sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) as mascots for our project resides in the fact that, like other marine mammals, sperm whales are endangered and particularly threatened by plastic marine litter. Dozens of these whales die every year due to inflammation caused by the presence of indigestible plastic in their stomach or due to entanglement in ghost (plastic-made) nets. More than 640,000 tons of nets, lines, pots, and traps used in commercial fishing are dumped and discarded in the sea every year and most of this material is made of polyethylene. Like other types of plastic, polyethylene is a non-biodegradable material, which uses considerable amounts of fossil fuels to be produced and takes centuries to decompose. It is therefore imperative to reduce its use and to recycle it as much as possible. As part of MAELSTROM's communication activities, three life-size whales were assembled and delivered, namely:

- i) in Portugal, at the headquarters of our partner CIIMAR.
- ii) in Italy: one whale at the new headquarters of our partner and project leader CNR-ISMAR (Venice, *Arsenale* area); another whale at the *Palazzina Canonica*, historical headquarters of CNR-ISMAR (Venice, city centre) where MAELSTROM's whale was part of the exhibition "*Antropocene*" designed to foster awareness on the impacts of humans on the planet Earth and as part of the 100^o anniversary of the Italian Research Council (CNR).

In June 2023 the consortium received an invitation to permanently display one of the whales at the Sergej Mašera Maritime Museum in Slovenia, a possibility that will undergo analysis during 2024, also depending on the remaining funds.

Figure 19 - MAELSTROM's recycled plastic sperm whale in Venice, Antropocene exhibit, June-July 2023

7.1.10 Press: TV and magazine articles

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/>

Around 70 articles have been published by local newspapers in Italy and in Portugal regarding the MAELSTROM and its public events. Articles and can be consulted on the project website under the section Media – Press Review.

MAELSTROM has also been showcased in the national television channels in multiple countries, namely:

- ITALY
 - RAI News | SCIENZIATI: *Inquinamento marino e strategie di contrasto*, 13/12/2023
<https://telprn.telpress.it/news/2023/12/13/2023121305585830824.MP4>
 - TG2 Venezia: *Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform*, 23/09/2022
<https://fb.watch/oXYurK-dWe/>
- PORTUGAL
 - PORTO CANAL: *Bubble Barrier de Vila do Conde* | 05/12/2023

- <https://youtu.be/qYV0ostZLRU?si=X5znM7Th8Qk0Hdjb>

- SPAIN

- RTVE: Efectos de los plásticos en los mares | 13/05/2023
https://www.rtve.es/play/videos/para-todos-la-2/efectos-restos-plasticos-mares/6886947/?fbclid=IwAR2iQEyIZNNLvQ_6lFjxsXV53U6SDxjIYHAuRmszEXt2QzDVSDNCgz7cHgA

- MALTA

- TVAM | Il-Futur magħna! Robot li jnaddaf il-qiegħ tal-baħar mill-plastic u sistema ta' pannelli solari fuq il-baħar! | 11.03.2023
<https://fb.watch/oXY5p9RgyJ/>

Table 2 - Branding Materials

Event's kit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logo Delivered • Leaflet and Brochure Delivered • PPT, Word and Poster templates Delivered • Roll-ups and flags Delivered • T-shirt and Bags Delivered • Pins Delivered
Videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video #1: Introduction to the project, 2021 Delivered • Video #2: MAELSTROM App, July 2022 Delivered • Video #3: Teaser Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, July 2022 Delivered • Video #4: Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, June 2022 Delivered • Video #5: Launch Event Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, November 2023 To be published by the end of the year • Video #6: Final Conference To be delivered in 2024 <p>Archive: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwGpE7VUFUsoiKdgFuZUvUQ</p>
Newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter #1 - 06/2021 Delivered • Newsletter #2 - 12/2021 Delivered • Newsletter #3 - 06/2022 Delivered • Newsletter #4 - 12/2022 Delivered • Newsletter #5 - 06/2023 Delivered • Newsletter #6 - 12/2023 in preparation • Newsletter #7 - 06/2024 • Newsletter #8 - 12/2024 <p>Archive: https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/</p>

Website	http://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/MaelstromH2020 • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/maelstrom-h2020/ • Twitter: https://twitter.com/H2020Maelstrom • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/maelstrom_h2020/ • You Tube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwGpE7VUFUsoiKdgFuZUvUQ
MAELDrops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAELDrop #1: The problem of marine litter • MAELDrop #2: How much litter is in the sea? • MAELDrop #3: Marine litter, from the sea back to the coast • MAELDrop #4: Many types of plastics • MAELDrop #5: Let's talk about polyethylene • MAELDrop #6: The nexus between plastic and climate change • MAELDrop #7: How the COVID-19 pandemics increases plastic generation and dispersion • MAELDrop #8: Studying marine litter from above with remote sensing • MAELDrop #9: Cetaceans, between yesterday's risks and today's risks • MAELDrop #10: Marine litter, a vehicle of transport for invasive species • MAELDrop #11: Bioplastics, biodegradable, and compostable plastics: first episode • MAELDrop #12: Let's de-plastify the Holidays! • MAELDrop #13: An international treaty against plastic • MAELDrop #14: A new pathology: plasticosis • MAELDrop #15: How old are microplastics in the sea? • MAELDrop #16: Oceanic birds and plastic exposure, a global assessment • MAELDrop #17: The approval of EU Nature Restoration Law • MAELDrop #18: The effects of plastics on human health • MAELDrop #19: Plastic pollution is also an environmental justice issue <p>Archive: https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maeldrops/</p>
MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews #1: Damien Sallé TECNALIA • MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews #2: Fantina Madricardo CNR-ISMAR • MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews #3: Davide Poletto Venice Lagoon Plastic Free • MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews #4: Carla Wessels The Great Bubble Barrier • MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews #5: Luis Vieira CIIMAR <p>Archive: https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-news/</p>

Whale sculptures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIIMAR Headquarters, Matosinhos - Portugal • CNR-ISMAR Headquarters, Venice - Italy • Palazzina Canonica, Venice - Italy <p>Request to display a plastic recycled whales at the Sergej Mašera Maritime Museum in Slovenia under evaluation.</p>
Press outreach	<p>https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/</p>

8 Dissemination strategy: an update for M36

Considering that both MAELSTROM's technologies were successfully implemented during 2023, also the dissemination efforts have grown and are expected to peak in the next year of the project.

The launch events of each technology held in June 2023 (Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in Venice) and on November 25th (Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde) proved to be very successful, seeing the presence of relevant institutional figures of each location. For what regards the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, launched in June 2023, dissemination efforts were translated into a significant interest of [Veritas](#) - the public company that manages the water and waste cycles in the Venice metropolitan area – in adopting the system to clean areas of the Venice Lagoon. Partners involved in the dialog process with stakeholder Veritas are CNR, Tecnalia, CNRS and Venice Lagoon Plastic Free.

As for the Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, the vice-president of the [Portuguese Environmental Agency](#) which attended the launch event in Vila do Conde, manifested his interest in accompanying the impact/environmental monitoring activities, hoping to implement the system in other rivers in Portugal. The consortium partner directly involved with local stakeholders in Portugal is mainly CIIMAR, with support from The Great Bubble Barrier and the University of Malta.

Within these contexts the communication group supports partner's efforts through communicative materials (mainly presentations and videos,) highlighting the main characteristics of both technologies and aimed at providing stakeholders with all the information needed in a clear and straight forward manner. Social media channels have also been a relevant tool to provide visibility of interested stakeholders on the

MAELSTROM's technologies and are often used with the purpose to create a relationship with the project.

Moreover, during the last 36 months, the MAELSTROM team has engaged in several own organized and external events, capacity-building actions, and demonstrative sessions (refer to Annexes 5 and 6). Although not directly in charge of such activities, in these occasions the communication team works alongside the consortium partners, as they represent important opportunities for disseminating project's achievements and products.

Dissemination efforts in 2024 will focus on the scientific papers published by the consortium and related to MAELSTROM's activities (e.g., monitoring, and environmental impacts from the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform and Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, AI for marine litter identification and sorting, etc.). Efforts will also align with the exploitation strategy being developed by partner Alpha and regarding project's products: App, Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, Robot for autonomous marine litter identification and sorting.

In line with the activities developed in the previous years, the communication team supports capacity building actions (task 9.3), stakeholder engagement processes (task 9.4) and the organization of project's events (task 9.5).

8.1 Support Capacity Building Actions | Task 9.3

MAELSTROM's capacity-building actions target three main groups:

- i) Project partners.
- ii) MAELSTROM App users.
- iii) Operators and Beneficiaries of the MAELSTROM technologies.

8.1.1 Project partners

A capacity building workshop for MAELSTROM's communication focal points was initially foreseen during the project's kick-off meeting however, due to covid constrains at the time (2021), the workshop was substituted by monthly meetings. So far twenty-seven online meetings took place, giving partners the chance to align on

main milestones, events, and future actions, as well as to make requests and or/discuss relevant ideas for project's communication and dissemination activities. It was during one of these communication meetings that the communication team suggested the creation of two scale models of the MAELSTROM's technologies, which could be easily transported and showcased during conferences and public events. Partners Tecnalia and The Great Bubble Barrier both agreed to produce these models using their own resources. Both demonstration kits have been widely exhibited during public events.

Figure 20 – Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform scale model at InnovAzul International Meeting on Knowledge and the Blue Economy, Cadiz, Spain, December 2022

Figure 21 – Bubble Barrier scale model at the UN Ocean Conference, Lisbon, June 2022

8.1.2 App users

During project clean-ups and info days, involved partners are expected to showcase the features and functionalities of the MAELSTROM app to environmental associations, volunteers, and marine litter practitioners. The app is not designed for the public, as it requires knowledge regarding different categories of plastics.

Partners Venice Lagoon Plastic Free and ISDI have conducted several clean-up activities in the Venice region using and showing the main features and functionalities of the MAELSTROM app to a wide range of local associations and volunteers. Similarly, CIIMAR in Portugal and Tecnalia in Spain have used the MAELSTROM App during public clean-up events. On this regard, CIIMAR has partnered with the *Trash Traveller Initiative* (<https://theplastichike.org/the-trash-cycle/>) and organized a joint clean up activity in Vila do Conde where the MAELSTROM app was presented to local environmental associations. Tecnalia has partner with the environmental association [La cara invisible del planeta](#) and the wellbeing association [Goozenup](#) for the same purposes.

To support the dissemination efforts, the communication team produced a dedicated video to publicize and disseminate the MAELSTROM App to other possible interested users already working in the field. Both the project brochure and website have a dedicated section to the MAELSTROM's App.

8.1.3 Operators and beneficiaries of MAELSTROM's technologies

Upon request or whenever the need will be felt, technical informative materials regarding MAELSTROM's technologies will be developed targeting operators and beneficiaries, such as waste management companies and municipalities of MAELSTROM's technologies pilot locations. The consortium will, during the next year, assess the needs of local operators on this regard, also based on the manifested interested by local stakeholders to keep the technologies, after the conclusion of the project.

8.2 Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes | Task 9.4

MAELSTROM actively looks for the creation of synergies among multi-level actors relating to the marine litter cycle field. Those include similar and complementary EU and national projects, partnerships with relevant public or private actors - such as municipalities and waste management and recycling companies - academia, NGOs, artists, and local associations that might be interested in connecting with and supporting the project. Stakeholder engagement and networking activities are led by Portuguese partner CIIMAR for activities in Portugal and by partners Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF), ISDI and CNR for activities in Italy.

As the stakeholder engagement activities often meet with communication and dissemination efforts, CIMA works in close synergy with them. Below are some major achievements:

- Three networking webinars were organized by the MAELSTROM partners CIIMAR (leader of the task), CNR, VLPF and CIMA with the support and participation of other partners.
 - The first webinar "*Inspiring Science and Society to tackle Marine Litter*" was held on 18/11/2021. The event aimed at identifying best practices and existing gaps among plastic-related stakeholders, from producers to recyclers so to direct future efforts coherently. Outcomes from the webinar contributed to the set-up of a Joint Strategy for Marine Litter Networking Actions (Deliverable under Work Package 7).
 - The second webinar "*Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Digital Services*" was held on 10/05/2022. Addressed at the scientific community, the workshop aimed to provide operational tools for collaborative scientific works on Marine Litter pollution using the EOSC digital services and is produced in collaboration with our twin projects In-No-Plastic and RELIANCE
 - The third webinar "*Biodiversity and Marine Litter: Co-detection and impacts*" was held on 10/02/2023 within the Air Centre Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays' initiative. The webinar focused on the co-detection and impacts of marine litter on marine biodiversity it was co-organized

with AIR Centre - Atlantic International Research Centre and GEO BON Marine Biodiversity Observation Network.

- Three stakeholders' meetings were organized in Venice with local and national stakeholders to highlight the current marine litter management system in Venice. Activities and efforts of various European projects were presented, each supporting the technological and cultural step needed towards sustainable marine litter management in Italy and across Europe. The last two stakeholders' meetings focused on explaining the functioning, results and potentialities of the MAELSTROM's Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform to local stakeholders so to promote its adoption after the projects will come to its conclusion.
- Two live demonstration/launch events were organized to present the MAELSTROM's technologies to national and local stakeholders from Italy (Venice) and Portugal (Vila do Conde)
- MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic submitted a Policy Brief at the United Nations Oceans Conference (UNOC) in June 2022, entitled "*8 Regulatory Changes that can Make Marine Litter Removal and Reintroduction in the Economy Viable at a Large Scale*". The policy proposal provided suggestions to incorporate plastic pollution limitations into current regulations, to establish mandatory plastic pollution monitoring actions and to promote autonomous plastic removal technologies for waterways.
- MAELSTROM's Consortium has submitted a Position Paper entitled: "*The need to align EC Directives to properly address Riverine-Marine Litter*". The aim of the paper is to support the inclusion of riverine-marine litter in the Water Framework Directive (WFD) metrics for the implementation of the assessment of the water quality in freshwater and transitional environments.
- Partner CIIMAR, with the support from partner CIMA have created an international database of funded projects and multiple-scale key stakeholders - created in the first year of the project is regularly updated to improve the network capacity

- MAELSTROM has endorsed the EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters and has joined the Mission Charter, contributing, and benefiting from a rich network of initiatives regarding marine litter and plastic pollution.
- MAELSTROM is part of the BlueMed Initiative, interacting with several other projects working in the Mediterranean region.
- A Memorandum of Understanding was established with the Ecopolietilene Consortium (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>): an Italian group composed of manufacturers, distributors, and recyclers of polyethylene goods. The Ecopolietilene Consortium is an autonomous non-profit system recognized by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea Protection. The consortium has provided the recycled plastic material from which our life-size whale models were built.
- A Memorandum of Understanding was established between the University of Bologna and Tecnalìa for the mentorship of a PhD student at the headquarters of Tecnalìa.
- A Memorandum of Understanding was established between the University of Bologna and CIIMAR for the internship of two master students:
 - Giorgio Simone: *Environmental Data collection and analysis for modelling litter pollution hotspots in the Ave estuary, Portugal, 2022* - MSc in Marine Biology, University of Bologna.
 - Claudia Pezzilli: *Marine pollution from source to sink, monitoring pollution in a river estuary in Portugal, 2022* - MSc in Marine Biology, University of Bologna.
- Other EU-funded projects and groups working in the marine litter field were contacted by the consortium and participated at MAELSTROM's workshops and events. Below is a list of engaged projects and institutions with which we have established an open dialogue regarding marine litter and plastic pollution:

Table 3 - EU funded projects engaged in MAELSTROM's events

Projects	
In-No-Plastic	https://www.innoplasic.eu/
Claim	https://www.claim-h2020project.eu/
GoJelly	https://gojelly.eu/
SeaClear	https://seaclear-project.eu/
ITA-HR INTERREG MARLESS	https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/marless
marGnet Consortium	https://www.margnet.eu/it/home/
BluMed Initiative	http://www.blumed-initiative.eu/
Reliance	https://www.reliance-project.eu/
BlueMissionMed	https://bluemissionmed.eu/
Winblue	https://winblue-project.eu/
Life Dream	https://www.life-dream.eu/
Reconmatic	https://www.reconmatic.eu/
Remedies	https://remedies-for-ocean.eu/
Inspire Europe	https://inspire-europe.org/
Prep4Blue	https://prep4blue.eu/

Table 4 - Institutional actors engaged in MAELSTROM's technologies implementation

Institutional Actors Italy (pilot: Venice)	
Venice Municipality	https://www.comune.venezia.it/
Gruppo Veritas - waste management body in Venice	https://www.gruppoveritas.it/
Venice Coast Guard	https://www.guardiacostiera.gov.it/organizzazione/direzione-marittima-di-venezia
Veneto Region	https://www.regione.veneto.it/

ARPA Veneto (Environmental Agency of the Veneto Region)	https://www.arpa.veneto.it/
Provveditorato Interregionale per le Opere Pubbliche per il Veneto, Trentino-Alto Adige e Friuli-Venezia Giulia	http://provveditoratovenezia.mit.gov.it/
Senator Andrea Ferrazzi, member of the Italian Parliament	https://www.senato.it/leg/18/BGT/Schede/Attsen/00032632.htm
WWF Italy	https://www.wwf.it/

Institutional Actors Portugal (pilot: Porto)	
Vila do Conde Municipality	https://www.cm-porto.pt/
LIPOR – waste management body in Northern Portugal	https://www.lipor.pt/pt/
APA – Portuguese Environmental Agency	https://apambiente.pt/
DOCAPESCA	https://www.docapesca.pt/
Águas do Norte – water management body in Northern Portugal	https://www.adnorte.pt/
Captaincy of Vila do Conde – National Maritime Authority	https://www.amn.pt/DGAM/Capitanias/VilaConde/Paginas/Capitania-do-Porto-de-Vila-do-Conde.aspx
CMIA – Environmental Monitoring and Interpretation Centre of Vila do Conde	https://www.cm-viladoconde.pt/pages/528

Table 5 - Private companies engaged with the MAELSTROM project

Companies	
Ecopolietilene Consortium (Italy)	https://ecopolietilene.it/
River Cleaning (Italy)	https://rivercleaning.com/it/
Clera.One (Slovenia)	https://www.clera.one/

WasteShark (The Netherlands)	https://www.wevolver.com/specs/wasteshark
Sintol srl (Italy)	https://sintol.it/
Everwave (Germany)	https://everwave.de/en/
Caracol & NextChem (Italy)	https://nextchem.it
IRIS (Italy)	https://www.irissrl.eu
Fish Flow (The Netherlands)	https://fishflowinnovations.nl/en/
Nanobay (Germany)	https://www.nanobay.com/
Probotica (Croatia)	https://www.probotica.hr/
NNL (Greece)	https://www.oilspillresponse.gr/
Ponikve (Croatia)	http://www.ekootokkrk.hr/en
Empower (Norway)	https://www.empower.eco/
EMI (Italy)	https://emiforpets.it
Infordata Sistemi srl	https://infordata.it/
MOLD srl	https://mold.it/

8.3 Support public and scientific events | Task 9.5

MAELSTROM's own events take place mainly in Italy and Portugal and are managed by local partners CNR-ISMAR (Italy), VLPF (Italy), ISDN (Italy) and CIIMAR (Portugal), with the technical and communicative support of CIMA Research Foundation. However, several other external events deserve our attention as they represent crucial opportunities for networking with a wide range of international stakeholders.

After MAELSTROM's participation at the United Nations Ocean Conference held in Lisbon 2022 - already described in the First Interim Communication and Dissemination report - we were pleased to learn that our project coordinator, Fantina Madricardo (CNR-ISMAR) was invited to integrate the Italian Delegation that took part at third session of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC-3) on Plastic Pollution, held at the UN Environment Programme headquarters in Nairobi from 13 to 19 November 2023. Other main highlights regarding MAELSTROM's events were:

- The EU Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters Events:
 - [The Mediterranean Lighthouse in Action](#) (Palermo, May 2023), where MAELSTROM has participated at the Blue Mission Med 1st Mediterranean Stakeholder Forum, under the Research & Education Table, in two sessions:
 - **Inspire and Inform:** where MAELSTROM's partner CIIMAR showcased MAELSTROM's main achievements in research, ocean literacy and social engagement.
 - **Blue Mission Med Stakeholder Forum:** a session dedicated to the identification of key steps to implement the Mission Lighthouse and to elaborate concrete actions (what and how) for each category.
 - [Sustainable Technologies for Marine Litter Removal and Recycling: the experience of the H2020 MAELSTROM project](#) (Rimini, 2023), workshop chaired by our project coordinator Fantina Madricardo (CNR-ISMAR), with Claudia Pecoraro (DG-RTD, EU Science & Innovation) during ECOMONDO's fair. MAELSTROM's partners explained the opportunities and the challenges faced while developing marine litter removal technologies - but also the role and the importance of stakeholder and

citizen involvement in addressing plastic pollution. The workshop was also an opportunity to dialogue with many other experts from EU funded projects (Remedies, Inspire Europe and Prep4Blue) which have illustrated their experiences in marine litter monitoring, removing and recycling, the lessons learnt, and the strategies put in place to overcome challenges.

- **Live Demonstrations/Launch Events of MAELSTROM's technologies**
 - [Live Demonstration/Launch Event of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform](#) (June 2023, Venice, Italy), at the presence of the Mayor of Venice
 - [Launch Event Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde](#) (November 2023, Portugal), at the presence of the Mayor of Vila do Conde, the Portuguese State Secretary for the Sea, and the Vice-President of the Portuguese Environmental Agency
- **Award**
 - [All-Atlantic Award Ceremony](#) (October 2023, Matosinhos, Portugal) where MAELSTROM has received the Award under the category Healthy Oceans and Resilient Coasts

Figure 22 – All-Atlantic Award Ceremony, October 2023

Alongside those events, and even if at a very local scale, the Sunset Beach Clean-up held in September 2023 in Vila do Conde, represented an important occasion to co-organize an event with the Municipality. The experience proved to be very beneficial both for what regarded the involvement of the community at the event itself and as a preparation of the Launch Event of the Bubble Barrier, held later in November. The Municipality has in fact expressed its interest to fully engage in co-organizing the Launch Event of the Bubble Barrier, providing all the technical and logistical support and ensuring the participation of high-level representatives such as the Portuguese State Secretary for the Sea and the Vice-President of the Portuguese Environmental Agency, alongside key stakeholders such as the Port Captainty Commander, the Director of Docapesca – Portos e Lotas, S.A. and Lipor.

An impressive number of events have been organized and attended by the MAELSTROM consortium, summarized on the tables below: table 1 refers to official MAELSTROM events, organized by the consortium, while table 2 refers to external events where MAELSTROM was invited and represented by its partners. ANNEX 5 provides further details on each event.

Figure 23 – Live demonstration/Launch Event Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, June 2023

Figure 24 – Live demonstration/Launch Event Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, November 2023

Figure 25 – Sunset beach Clean-up Vila do Conde, September 2023

Table 6 - MAELSTROM Events (Task 9.5)

	Title	Status	N. participants
Kick-off meeting	MAELSTROM Kick Off Meeting (online)	03-04-05/02/2021	Consortium members, an average of 2 per partner (28)
Dissemination Events	1 st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy - joint event with In-No-Plastic H2020 project	03/06/2020	50
	2 nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy - joint event with In-No-Plastics H2020 project	06/2022	70
	3 rd International Workshop Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy - joint event with In-No-Plastic H2020 project	06/2023	75
	Launch Event Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform - Venice, Italy	06/2023	100
	Launch Event Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde - Vila do Conde, Portugal	25/11/2023	150
	MAELSTROM Final Workshop & Conference - Porto, Portugal	2024	
Clean ups & Info Days	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Days - Venice, Italy on World Ocean/World Environmental Day and EU Beach Clean-up campaign	05/06/2021 02/06/2022 06/2023 06/2024	50 50 75
	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Days - Porto/Vila do Conde, Portugal on World Clean Up Day	17/09/2021 09/2022 09/2023 09/2024	100 80 120
	Yearly clean ups (2 in total) & Info Days - San Sebastian, Spain	08/2022 06/2023	65 65
Stakeholders Meetings and Demonstration Workshops	Yearly stakeholders' meetings (3 in total) - Venice, during the International Venice Boat Show	06/2021 06/2022 06/2023	30 50 50
	Inspiring Science and Society to tackle Marine Litter	18/11/2021	63
	Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud	10/05/2022	26

Webinars	Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays with MAELSTROM: Biodiversity and Marine Litter: Co-detection and Impacts	10/02/2023	XX
	One Ocean, One Health: Current Perspectives on Marine Litter Impacts on Ecosystem and Human Health	2024	
	TBA	2024	
Capacity Building Actions	Capacity Building on Communication & Stakeholder Engagement approaches. Target: MAELSTROM's partners/communication focal points	Replaced by monthly meetings	Communication Focal Points (average 15 people/month)
	Marine litter monitoring using the MAELSTROM App -- during clean-up in Venice and Vila do Conde in 2022	2022	60
	Marine litter monitoring using the MAELSTROM App -- during clean-up in Venice and Vila do Conde in 2023	2023	60

Commentato [IG1]: Ask Luis

Table 7 - External Events & Conferences attended in the last thirty-six months

Title	Link	Partner attending
ITEM project online workshop	https://www.cnr.it/it/progetti-di-ricerca/progetto/40295/ctn02-00059-9948371-item-dit-ad022-173	13/01/2021 CNR
EU Biovoices Project Conference	https://www.biovoices.eu/#	14/01/2021 CNR
Blue Med Final Conference	http://www.blumed-initiative.eu/blumed-final-conference/	22-23-24/02/2021 CNR
Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul	https://ambienteportugal.pt/eventos/ecosistemas-marinhos-e-economia-azul	23/04/2021 CIIMAR
marGnet and MAELSTROM Demonstration activity: operation of a prototype for recycling of marine waste and the production of maritime fuel		14/05/2021 CNR

European Maritime Day - Session BLUINVEST	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/events/2021-european-maritime-day_en	21/05/2021 CNR
NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies	https://ncr-web.org/events/ncr-may-lecture/	26/05/2021 Deltares
EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter'	https://bioplasticseurope.eu/media/pages/news-events/horizon-2020-cluster-meeting-on-marine-litter/21c23f102f-1646989939/agenda.pdf	01/06/2021 CNR
Venice International Boat Show	InfoPoint on Marine litter	29/05/2021 - 6/06/2021 CNR
Online seminar in the framework of the event "Arazzi del Mare"	Online seminar	8 /06/2021 CNR
AreaAperta Primavera	https://comunicazione.cnr.it/evento/398/evento-conferenza-oreoperta	16/06/2021 CNR
BlueMed Hackathon 2021	https://www.cnr.it/it/news/10199/una-sfida-tra-idee-il-blued-med-hackathon-ideas-and-solutions-for-a-healthy-plastic-free-mediterranean-sea	17/06/2021 CNR
EMRA2021 Robotics	https://emra-21.marinerobotics.eu/	08/07/2021 CNR
BlueMed - Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter	http://www.blued-med-initiative.eu/ports-harbours-venice-september-14-2021/	14/09/2021 CNR
"Arazzi del Mare" organized by QUANTIA - ITALIA	Seminar on marine litter	24/09/2021 CNR
Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS"	https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/research/lighthouse-projects-fraunhofer-initiatives/innovation-platform-sustainable-subsea-solutions.html	23/09/2021 TECNALIA
IHOBE Comisión Basura Marina para el País Vasco	https://www.ihobe.eus/agenda/urban-klima-2050-colaboracion-multisectorial-para-financiar-y-reducir-brecha-adaptacion-en-pais-vasco-2?fbclid=IwAR1eN9T4nITs8hUlv3hPz8jjBD4YpUeIgyKgZcuacujWllOzHm_448Q	28/09/2021 TECNALIA
Scienza in Villa	https://www.scienzainvilla.com	01/10/2021 – 03/10/2021 CNR-ISMAR
ECOMONDO 2021- Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants	https://www.ecomondo.com/link/seminari-e-convegni/e18938877/transforming-plastics-litter-into-new-chemicals-opportunities-and-challenges-for-innovative-pyrolysis-plants.html	26/10/2021 CNR

ECOMONDO 2021 -The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean Sea towards the 2030 targets: the strategy developed by the plastic producing and transforming operators of the area	http://www.blueded-initiative.eu/pilot-ecomondo-2021-rimini/	26/10/2021 CNR
ECOMONDO 2021 - Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean Sea	http://www.blueded-initiative.eu/ecomondo-2021-oct-27/	27/10/2021 CNR
Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/node/7000?fs=e&se=cl	03/02/2022 CNR
EXPO Dubai: Multidisciplinary and systemic approaches for the rational use of resource and sustainability	https://www.isafom.cnr.it/index.php/en/attivita/divulgazione/tutte-le-news/373-dubai-expo-2020-land-city-sea-scape-intelligence-multidisciplinary-and-systemic-approaches-for-the-rational-use-of-resource-and-sustainability	14/03/2022 CNR
Jornadas do Mar: New Solutions for the Sustainable Removal and Management of Marine Litter	https://www.jornadasdomar.com/schedule	26/03/2022 CIIMAR
The Trash Cycle Initiative - Vila do Conde Clean Up	https://theplastichike.org/the-trash-cycle/	03/06/2022
XI Edition of the Environment Forum: "Removal and Sustainable Management of Marine Litter: Rethinking the Present, Designing the Future"	https://sigarra.up.pt/feup/pt/noticias_geral.ver_noticia?p_nr=130450	05/04/2022 CIIMAR
GEOHAB 2022 – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping	https://geohab.org/geohab-2022/	16/05/2022-20/05/2022 CNR
EMRA Workshop "European Marine Robotics & Applications Workshop (EMRA) 2022"	https://noc-events.co.uk/emra-2022	16/06/2022 TECNALIA
AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS - within BIEMH22 trade fair	https://biemh.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/en/conferences/automation-robotic-talks/	17/06/2022 TECNALIA
PLASTICA E CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI, UN MARE DA DIFENDERE Meeting co-organized with UNESCO, Greenpeace Italia and the NGO We are here Venice	https://www.cnr.it/it/nota-stampa/n-11193/plastica-e-cambiamenti-climatici-un-mare-da-difendere	22/06/2022 CNR
UN Ocean Conference	https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-	25/06/2022 CIIMAR, VLPF, TGBB

Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event	04/Concept%20Note%202022%20UNOC%20Local%20and%20Regional%20Gov%20Forum_REVISED_7April_for%20website%20%281%29.pdf	
UN Ocean Conference Official Session Addressing Marine Pollution	https://sdgs.un.org/events/addressing-marine-pollution-45736	27/06/2022 CIIMAR, VLPF, TGBB
UN Ocean Conference One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Event	https://oceansciencebusiness2sea.b2match.io/	28/06/2022 CIIMAR, VLPF, TGBB
UN Ocean Conference <i>EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action</i>	https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marine-litter-monitoring-to-inform-action/	29/06/2022 CIIMAR, VLPF, TGBB
UN Ocean Conference The Charter for the Mission "Restores our Ocean and Waters by 2030"	https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/charter-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2022-jun-30_en	30/06/2022 CIIMAR, VLPF, TGBB
ERF2022 - European Robotics Forum - Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop	https://erf2022.eu/	28-29/06/2022 TECNALIA
The 7th International Marine Debris Conference is taking place this week in Busan (Republic of Korea)	https://internationalmarinedebrisconference.org/	18-23/09/2022 VLPF
Marine Litter and Circular Economy workshop organized by the Interreg Italy-Croatia Programme MARELESS project. 26/11/2022	https://programming14-20.italy-croatia.eu/web/marless	26/11/2022 CNR
Black Sea CONNECT Marine Litter Action Forum (14th and 15th of	http://connect2blacksea.org/marine-litter-action-forum/	14-15/11/2022 CIIMAR
InnovAzul 2nd International Meeting on Knowledge and the Blue Economy - Open Innovation Session	https://aquabt.com/event/innovazul-2nd-international-meeting-on-knowledge-and-the-blue-economy/	29/11/2023 TECNALIA
Pan-European digital assets supporting research communities - Benefits & Opportunities	https://eoscfuture.eu/eventsfuture/webinar-pan-european-digital-assets-supporting-research-communities-benefits-opportunities/	5-6/12/2022 VLPF, CIIMAR, CNR
Kick Off Meeting Horizon CSA BluemissionMed	https://bluemissionmed.eu/	27/01/2023 CNR
EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters 1st Annual Forum	https://icfnext.swoogo.com/MissionForum2023	17/02/2023 TGBB
AI for Good Webinar: Sustainable robots: What does it take for a robot to be sustainable?	https://aiforgood.itu.int/event/sustainable-robots-what-does-it-take-for-a-robot-to-be-sustainable/	28/02/2023 TECNALIA

	take-for-a-robot-to-be-sustainable/	
Advancing the Un Sustainable Development Goals with Autonomous Robots	https://erf2023.sdu.dk/.../phd-award-finalists-pitches-2/	14-16/03/2023 TECNALIA
CINEA Workshop Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/events/workshop-ocean-health-observation-2023-04-17_en	17/04/2023 CNR
GEOHAB 2023	https://geohab.org/geohab-2023/	5-12/05/2023 CNR
Antropocene Exhibition	https://www.cnr.it/it/antropocene-terra-ferro-fuoco	6/05/2023 CIMA, CNR
European Maritime Day	https://european-maritime-day-2023.b2match.io/?fbclid=IwAR15T6iNZBh4SQWpkowsR2WBnewnwEdDIA8y-leYSY67quM2Ove8AnDXiDY	24-25/05/2023 ISDI
EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters – The Mediterranean Lighthouse in Action	https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-by-2030-the-mediterranean-lighthouse-in-action/?fbclid=IwARITu_TknAJnr0UhsIFTpFGwUmlPs6t6AOqg-oeqJHnBS4xLqgw_dG1jiQ	30/05 – 01/06/2023 CNR, CIIMAR
2013 – 2023: 10 years of the Galway Statement	https://allatlanticocean.org/events/10-years-of-the-galway-statement/	5-6/07/2023 CIIMAR
Ciência Viva - Science and Ocean Beyond the Horizon	https://www.encontrociencia.pt/2023/pt	5/07/2023 CIIMAR
Portuguese Conference on Marine Litter and Microplastics,	https://aplixomarinho.org/3cplm/	21-22/09/2023 CIIMAR
Scienza in Villa	https://www.memorialegrandeguevra.it/	23/09/2023 CNR
Ocean Best Practices (OBPS) Workshop VII - Challenge 1 – Understand and beat marine pollution	https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/community-engagement/workshops/ocean-practices-obps-workshop-vii-09-13-oct-2023-online/ocean-practices-obps-workshop-vii-registration-and-agenda/#:-text=The%20OBPS%20Workshop%20VII%2C%202023,Decade%20Actions%20and%20Programmes%20participation	17/10/2023 CNR
10th Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference	https://atlantic-maritime-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news-and-events/events/atlantic-stakeholder-platform-conference-2023	18-19/10/2023 CIIMAR, CNR
TREC - Traversing European Coastlines Expedition	https://www.embl.org/about/info/trec/expedition/	26/11/2023 CIIMAR

ECOMONDO	https://www.ecomondo.com/	7-10/11/2023 CNR, CIMA, CIIMAR, VLFP, TGBB, TECNALIA
UNEP INC-3 Plastics Treaty	https://www.unep.org/inc-plastic-pollution/session-3	13-19/11/2023 CNR
Conference on the Protection of Waters and Seas from Plastics and Micro-plastics Pollution	https://www.adriatic-ionion.eu/conference-on-the-protection-of-waters-and-seas-from-plastics-and-micro-plastics-pollution/	29/11/2023 CNR

8.4 Scientific work and peer reviewed publications

8.4.1 Peer reviews publications

Iglesias, M. Lupiac, L. R. Vieira, S.C. Antunes, J. Mira-Veiga, I. Sousa-Pinto, A. Lobo (2023): *Socio-economic factors affecting the distribution of marine litter: The Portuguese case study*. Marine Pollution Bulletin, 193, 115168. doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115168

M. Gouttefarde, M. Rodriguez, C. Barrelet, P.-E. Hervé, V. Creuze, et al. *The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform: An Underwater Cable-Driven Parallel Robot for Marine Litter Removal*. *Cable-Driven Parallel Robots*, S. Caro, T. Bruckmann and A. Pott eds., Springer, 2023 (Sixth International Conference on Cable-Driven Parallel Robots, CableCon 2023). <https://hal-lirmm.ccsd.cnrs.fr/lirmm-04261099v1/document>

8.4.2 Master thesis

Olatz Ortega MSc Erasmus Mundus 2022 (concluded). *Marine litter characterization and awareness actions in the NW coast of Portugal*. Erasmus Mundus Joint MAS in environmental Contamination and Toxicology, University of Porto.

Léa Josse MSc internship 2021: *Hydrodynamical conditions of shallow water estuaries and their influence in marine litter transport patterns*. MA in Fluid mechanics, energy, and environment, ENSEEIHT, Toulouse, France.

Amine Mohammed MSc internship 2022 (ongoing): *Implementation of an estuarine numerical model to represent hydrodynamic patterns and marine litter transport*. MA in marine engineering, SeaTech, Engineering School of the University of Toulon, France.

Maite Lupiac internship equivalent to MSc thesis 2022 (ongoing): *Characterization and analysis of Portuguese marine litter and its link with estuarine hydrodynamics*. MA in Fluid mechanics, energy, and environment, ENSEEIHT, Toulouse, France.

Daniela Padilha MSc thesis 2021/2022 (concluded): *Avaliação do Lixo Marinho e Microplásticos nas Águas de Transição do rio Ave*. MA Ecology and Environment, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto.

Rui Moreira MSc thesis 2021/2022 (ongoing): *Avaliação do estado do ecossistema e da qualidade das águas de transição do rio Ave*. MA Ecology and Environment, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto.

8.5 Young Generations

Figure 26 – Sunset beach Clean-up Vila do Conde, September 2023

Besides having a strong presence at scientific and technological events, MAELSTROM also wishes to create awareness in younger generations, welcoming children, and teenagers to volunteer and participate at project's clean-ups and info days. Whenever possible, during clean-ups/info-days stands and activities for children and families are foreseen, often in partnership with local actors.

Moreover, the project has developed awareness raising activities regarding plastic pollution with schools in Venice and Vila do Conde, respectively.

During the school year 2021-2022, three seminars and a field activity on marine litter clean-up and monitoring engaged two classes of the Albert Einstein High School of Venice. The activities were part of the civic education program and aimed at raising students' awareness on marine litter and to demonstrate the technological solutions proposed by MAELSTROM. Students were also asked during their daily activities to think about which disposable plastic products could be replaced with other more sustainable materials and to share their ideas and solutions in a specially created WhatsApp chat. Below are the details of the activities conducted with the classes (total of about 45 participants per event/activity).

1. Seminar on marine litter and its impact on ecosystems (online, January 27, 2022)
2. Seminar on microplastics and their impact on ecosystems (in-person, February 17, 2022)
3. Focus on the GHOST, marGnet and MAELSTROM projects (online April 28, 2022).
4. Participation in a clean-up campaign in Pellestrina beach in collaboration with MAELSTROM project partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (May 26, 2022).

Figure 27 - Seminar on microplastics at the Albert Einstein High School of Venice, February 2022

Figure 28 - Clean up activity in Pellestrina Beach with students from the Albert Einstein High School of Venice, May 2022

In Portugal activities were developed with the School Cluster Dr. Carlos Pinto Ferreira in Vila do Conde, where MAELSTROM's Bubble Barrier is implemented. Students have initially attended a scientific seminar held by CIIMAR researchers on the causes and impacts of marine litter and plastic pollution and have then been engaged in a clean-up activity at the local beach, supported by CIIMAR researchers.

Figure 29 - Clean up activity in Vila do Conde with students from the Dr. Carlos Pinto Ferreira School, Junqueira (Vila do Conde), Portugal, April 2023

9 Internal Communication

As part of the communication activities, significant efforts are made towards building a participatory and supportive environment among the consortium's members. The decision to substitute a one-off capacity building workshop on communication (initially planned for the kick-off meeting in presence) by monthly meetings proved to be beneficial, as it allows for a regular contact among communication focal points, and to understand their needs and suggestions. At the date of this report, twenty-seven communication meetings have been carried out, each focusing on a specific topic, normally aligned with relevant project's events or events to be attended by partners. Communication meetings are called via email by the communication coordinator (CIMA) which asks focal points to indicate their availability using the Doodle platform; once the date is set, the meeting takes place online, using the MS Teams platform.

Alongside regular monthly meeting, complementary meetings are also set within smaller working groups whenever necessary (e.g., only partners involved in the organization of a specific event). Considering the positive results, the communication team intends to maintain monthly meetings as well as specific meetings among project partners whenever justified.

10 Conclusions

The present document reports, on detail, the outcomes of the communication and dissemination activities implemented within the MAELSTROM project in the last thirty-six months.

Looking back in time, it is impressive to notice the number of events, activities, milestones, and visibility outcomes achieved so far. We interpret this as the result of the consortium's high level of expertise and will to collaborate, support and engage with the mission and activities proposed by the MAELSTROM project.

The work of the communication and dissemination team is extremely facilitated by such a dynamic and collaborative environment and all the positive outcomes must be acknowledge to the collective efforts put in place by partners.

Future efforts will focus on maintaining MAELSTROM's internal environment as collaborative as possible - through regular dialog opportunities (monthly meetings) - to preserve and, if possible, to increase MAELSTROM's reputation within the international community - especially in the pilot locations - and to support the exploitation strategy currently being developed, so to guarantee that all efforts will find continuity, towards a plastic-less global society - the ultimate goal of the MAELSTROM project!

ANNEX 1 - Communication and dissemination procedures regarding third parties' involvement

The communication and dissemination guidelines regarding the involvement of Third Parties follow two different approaches depending on if referring to institutional/in-kind parties or to monetary/financing third parties.

A shared table regarding third parties' involvement was created on the MAELSTROM project channel on MS Teams where partners are expected to insert information and details regarding Parties willing to be involved in the project's activities. It was agreed that partners wishing to establish partnerships with third parties for activities happening within the MAELSTROM project shall inform the Project Manager (CNR-ISMAR) beforehand which, in case of possible ethical issues or conflict of interests will activate the Steering Committee to demand for a shared analysis and final decision.

Institutional and In-Kind Parties

Whenever requested and if considered to benefit a foreseen action and group of partners, every institutional/in-kind support will be fully acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or by the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials (ex. Venice or Porto Municipalities logos), tagged on social media, and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

In the case that the institutional/in-kind support offered is considered to benefit only one partner, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the partnership/agreement. In this case, if the support received by the partner will be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing shall be mentioned, without creating a visual association (no logos together). In case the partner uses the support received for activities that do not relate to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure A1 - Communication procedures regarding institutional and in-kind third parties' involvement

Monetary/Financing Third Parties

Whenever requested, and if considered to benefit a group of partners, every monetary/financial support will be fully full acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials, tagged on social media and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

In the case monetary/financial support is considered to benefit only one partner, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the partnership/agreement. If the support received by the partner is to be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing percentages shall be mentioned, without creating a visual association (no logos together). Moreover, the partner benefiting from the monetary support shall clearly state the co-funding proportion being received, based on the total funding received by the European Union within the MAELSTROM project. In the case that the partner uses the support received for activities not related to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure A2 - Communication procedures regarding financial third parties' involvement

Figure A3 - Communication procedures regarding third parties' involvement graph flow

ANNEX 2 - MAELDrops

MAELDrop #1 | The problem of marine litter

April 21, 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-1-the-problem-of-marine-litter/>

Day after day, coming together, raindrops fill the rivers and run into the sea. In the same way, we also want to create information drops which will fill our heads with thoughts, ideas and solutions related to marine litter and to MAELSTROM's goals: please welcome MAELDrops! How does marine litter damage the coastal ecosystems? Are all plastics the same? What can we do to limit this problem, and how does MAELSTROM aim to tackle it? So, let's get started, come along with us and be part of the move!

Seas and oceans play an important role for our planet. They influence the climate, support the life of many species, and sustain fundamental human activities. However, the well-being of marine ecosystems is put at risk by several anthropogenic factors, including litter.

Litter, whether lost directly along the coastline or delivered to the sea by rivers, wind, or urban run-off, has an important ecological impact on marine life. As highlighted in a report published by the European Commission's JRC [1], litter can cause direct damage, for example by entangling or blocking the stomach/intestine of animals that accidentally ingest it. Moreover, the litter can cause indirect damage, for example by inducing a false sense of satiation, acting as vectors for toxic substances and compromising the animals' general ability to feed themselves.

Among marine litter, plastics are the most abundant. These are both large fragments and waste or very small particles resulting from the degradation and fragmentation of larger items. These are the microplastics, smaller than 5 mm, which accumulate along the food web and, as a result, can even reach the food we consume [2].

What will MAELSTROM do to mitigate the litter issue? Our project will develop and test new environmentally sustainable technologies for removing litter accumulated on the seafloor or in the water column in coastal areas. MAELSTROM will then define and implement an integrated assessment approach (IAA) to evaluate the effectiveness of these technologies. This approach will support the Marine Strategy Framework Directive of European Union and assess the positive and/or negative impact of the MAELSTROM litter remediation actions on coastal marine ecosystems and local economies. The IAA will consider both macro and microlitter.

References:

[1] <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/harm-caused-marine-litter>

[2] <https://echo.europa.eu/hot-topics/microplastics>

SEAS AND OCEANS play an **IMPORTANT ROLE FOR OUR PLANET** but they are put at risk by several anthropogenic factors including litter

PLASTICS are the most abundant including microplastics which accumulate along the food web and can **REACH THE FOOD WE CONSUME**

LITTER can cause both direct and indirect **DAMAGE TO MARINE LIFE** compromising animals general well-being

MAELSTROM aims to mitigate this issue by testing technologies for **LITTER REMOVAL FROM COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS** preventing its accumulation and degradation

MAELDROPS #1

The infographic is a vertical layout with a central image of a duck swimming in water with a piece of white foam floating nearby. The background is divided into colored sections: dark blue at the top, light blue on the left, orange on the right, and green at the bottom. The MAELSTROM logo and "MAELDROPS #1" are centered in the white space between the light blue and orange sections.

MAELDrop #2 | How much litter is in the sea?

May 31, 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-2-how-much-litter-is-in-the-sea/>

In [MAELDrop #1](#), we have introduced you to the problem of marine litter. But what kind of litter is marine litter? And in which quantities is it present in the oceans?

The United Nation Environment Programme [defines](#) marine litter as “any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment”. As we reported, the majority of it is plastics. Assessing the amount of plastics in the sea is not easy, as estimates can give different results depending on the methodology used.

[According to the European Commission](#), more than 150 million tons of plastic are accumulated in the oceans and unfortunately, these quantities are increasing: between 4.6 and 12.7 million tons of plastic are added each year, and it could reach 29 million tons by 2040.

These are impressive numbers, which should be considered even more worrisome considering that most marine litter consists of materials that degrade slowly. As a result, their continuous and increasing dispersion in the seas leads to a **progressive accumulation**. In this way the marine litter becomes pervasive in all the environments increasing the risks for all the food web and the habitats.

What will MAELSTROM do to mitigate the accumulation of marine litter?

There are two activities in our project that will help reduce marine litter. On the one hand, we will test and implement two innovative technologies that will allow for the removal of litter from the seabed and from the superficial layers of the water column – we will present them to you soon! But we can't tackle the problem with technology alone – we need shared good practices and everyone's help to preserve our marine ecosystems. Being so, as part of the project we have organized info days and clean up campaigns where we will not be only collecting litter that has accumulated on the coast, but also creating awareness regarding marine litter impacts and spreading good behaviours to mitigate its impacts in coastal ecosystems and in our life!

More than
150 MILLION
TONS OF PLASTIC
are accumulated
in the oceans

These
QUANTITIES ARE
INCREASING.

Between **4.6 and 12.7 MILLION TONS**
of plastic are added each year

Since most marine litter consists of
MATERIALS THAT DEGRADE SLOWLY,
there is a **PROGRESSIVE**
ACCUMULATION in the seas

MAELSTROM will test and
implement two innovative
TECHNOLOGIES
FOR LITTER REMOVAL.

But we can't tackle the problem with
technology alone: discover
WHAT YOU CAN DO TO HELP US!

STAY TUNED...

MAELDrop #3 | Marine litter, from the sea back to the coast

June 2, 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-3-marine-litter-from-the-sea-back-to-the-coast/>

In the last [MAELDrops](#), we've told how much litter is found in the seas and oceans, and the damage it causes to ecosystems. But waste doesn't just stay in the water.... Carried by winds and rivers, or even abandoned directly in the sea, currents can concentrate waste, accumulating in large areas, as the famous [Great Pacific Garbage Patch](#). But not all litter remains at sea. Ocean currents, in fact, often bring it back to shore ... and so we find it on our coasts and beaches. In addition to representing a possible **economic and landscape damage** (who likes to sunbathe surrounded by garbage?), here too litter can put at risk our ecosystems. According to a recent [technical report](#) by the European Union's JRC, a beach can be considered clean if less than 20 pieces of trash are found every 100 linear meters of coastline: this is a significant value, if we consider that between 2015 and 2016 many European beaches had on average 150 objects every 100 meters.

Understanding how much and what type of waste is found along the coasts is important to design effective strategies and policies aimed at reducing it. In this sense, **clean up campaigns are a tool of enormous importance**, because on the one hand they help to clean beaches and, on the other hand, they contribute to collect data on the marine litter. In addition, they represent a valuable opportunity to raise public awareness on the problem of marine litter.

What about MAELSTROM? We too believe in the importance of clean ups! The problem of marine litter, in fact, cannot be addressed only with science and technology: all citizens can commit to reduce it, both through small daily gestures and by participating in the clean-up events... Like the one that will be held in [June 5th in Venice!](#) Stay tuned to learn more, in the coming days we will provide all the information about the event, the first – but certainly not the last – of our project!

<p>NOT ALL LITTER REMAINS AT SEA : ocean currents often bring it back to shore ... and so we FIND IT ON OUR COASTS AND BEACHES.</p>	
<p>...contribute TO COLLECT DATA ON THE MARINE LITTER and represent a valuable opportunity to raise PUBLIC AWARENESS</p>	

MAELDrop #4 | Many types of plastics

July 26, 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-4-many-types-of-plastics/>

In our MAELDrops, we have mentioned that most of the marine litter is plastic. But what exactly is plastic?

Plastics are a set of polymeric materials, made up of many equal and repeated units. There are diverse types of plastics and each one has distinct characteristics according to the type of polymer from which it is made. Even in a simple bottle of water we can find [two types of plastics](#): the bottle itself is usually made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which is light and resistant, whereas the cap is often made of polypropylene (PP), which is slightly harder and more heat resistant. Plastics play an important role for human activities. Just think, for example, of how many medical devices, from disposable gloves to catheters, are made of plastic. However, if not responsibly managed and disposed, plastics can become a severe problem for ecosystems, with impacts on our own health. One of the strategies to mitigate the problem, in addition to limiting production whenever possible, is to recycle and re-use plastic materials within in a circular economy perspective. To do so, it is necessary to consider the distinct types of plastics and choose appropriate recycling treatments accordingly.

What about MAELSTROM? From the marine litter collected by our technologies, plastics will be separated thanks to a robot based on an artificial intelligence system. In accordance with the [European circular economy action plan](#), plastics will then be recycled through 3 innovative processes: additive and compounding, hot pressing, and low temperature pyrolysis, which will allow to recycle most of the plastic waste. Materials which will not be directed to recycling will be used for primary energy generation and second-generation fuel and will power MAELSTROM's underwater cable-robot for marine waste collection... creating a self-sustaining cycle!

NOT ALL PLASTICS ARE THE SAME!
There are diverse types of plastics, with distinct **CHARACTERISTICS AND PROPERTIES**

2 PET
2 HDPE
3 PVC
4 LDPE
5 PP
6 PS
7 OTHER

MAELDROPS #4

COLLECTING AND RECYCLING PLASTICS ARE KEY to limit its accumulation on ecosystems, but it requires **PROPER IDENTIFICATION AND SORTING**

MAELDROPS #4

MAELSTROM will use a **ROBOT BASED ON AI TO SEPARATE PLASTICS** from the waste collected in rivers' hotspots in Italy and Portugal

5 PP
2 PET

MAELDROPS #4

Based on single characteristics it will direct plastic waste to **INNOVATIVE RECYCLING PROCESSES**, or when not compatible, it will use it to power MAELSTROM's technologies, creating **A SELF-SUSTAINING CYCLE!**

MAELDROPS #4

MAELDrop #5 | Let's talk about polyethylene

November 4, 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-5-lets-talk-about-polyethylene/>

Some time ago [we mentioned](#) the fact that there is not just one type of plastic, but many, each one of them with its own properties that influence their recycling feasibility.

Among the several widespread plastics we use daily, today we will focus on **polyethylene**. Why?

Firstly, because polyethylene is a very versatile polymer, which can be moulded into many different shapes and objects, both for everyday and industrial uses [1]. Some examples are kitchen objects such as jugs or cutting boards, children's toys in parks, drainpipes, and many others, in a very long list. The second reason is that polyethylene is **completely recyclable** which, considering its wide diffusion, makes it an important type of plastic to consider in terms of **circular economy**!

It is for this reason that we have chosen recycled polyethylene as the material to make our MAELSTROM mascot whales! We have already introduced you one of the three sperm whales that will accompany us in the next years of work last September, during the [Clean Up in Porto](#), organized by our partner [CIIMAR](#). Two more family members will follow soon!

The whales were made possible thanks to the support of the Italian [consortium Ecopolietilene](#) and will help us to disseminate knowledge on marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems and on sharing good practices regarding innovative plastic removal and recycling technologies. In this way, we will join forces to protect habitat of our sperm whales and of the many other marine species put at risk by the accumulation of marine litter!

POLYETHYLENE is one of the most common types of plastics...and one of the **MOST RECYCLABLE TOO !**

It is therefore a **GOOD RESOURCE** from a **CIRCULAR ECONOMY** perspective.

That's why **MAELSTROM** has used recycled polyethylene to make **ITS SPERM WHALE MASCOTS !**

Which will join us in **SPREADING KNOWLEDGE** on **MARINE LITTER** impacts & **PLASTIC REMOVAL AND RECYCLING** technologies !

HDPE

MAELDROPS #5

The infographic features a dark blue background with white and yellow text. It includes a recycling symbol and a photo of a group of people standing next to a large, black, cylindrical structure made of recycled polyethylene, which is a sperm whale mascot. A vertical banner to the right of the photo provides more information about the project.

MAELDrop #6 | The nexus between plastic and climate change

December 1, 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-6-the-nexus-between-plastic-and-climate-change/>

The United Nations conference on climate change, COP26, has just concluded, confirming the commitment to try to keep the increase in the average global temperature within 1.5 C at the end of the century. There is much to do to achieve this goal, and there are many fronts on which to act. Plastic production is among them.

In fact, as the UNEP report "[From Pollution to Solution: a global assessment of marine litter and plastic pollution](#)" published a few days before the start of COP26 highlights that plastic production led to the emission of 1.7 gigatons of CO2 equivalent in 2015. The authors estimate, moreover, that this figure will increase by about 6.5 times by 2050, reaching an amount that is around 15% of the global carbon budget.

In addition to the risks that plastics poses to ecosystems and to human health, which we have discussed in [MAELDrop 1](#), we must consider that plastics also pose a threat to climate crisis mitigation.

The report also warns that, by 2040, the volume of plastic in the sea could triple. Meanwhile, recycling rates remain below 10%, and unfortunately biodegradable plastics are unlikely to be a solution to the problem. These materials have long degradation times, during which they pose risks to ecosystems as it happens with non-biodegradable plastics. For this reason, the report concludes that synergistic interventions are needed to address the problem. These include circular economy approaches, but also initiatives aimed at changing consumer's behaviours regarding single-use plastics.

What about MAELSTROM? Our mission is perfectly in line with the report's conclusions: in fact, we develop solutions to face the problem of the plastic already accumulated in the coastal environment acting on the entire "life cycle" of marine litter: we aim at understanding where marine litter is concentrated, identify it by type, remove it, recycle it and insert it back into the market chain. Following a circular economy approach plastics will be given a new life while avoiding the production of new plastic and in this way protecting coastal ecosystems and our climate.

<p>A new UNEP REPORT, published a few days before the start of COP26, highlights that in 2015 PLASTIC PRODUCTION led to the emission of 1.7 GIGATONNES OF CO₂ EQUIVALENT</p>	
<p>Synergistic interventions are needed to address the problem. These include CIRCULAR ECONOMY approaches but also initiatives aimed at changing CONSUMER'S BEHAVIOURS regarding SINGLE-USE PLASTICS</p>	

MAELDrop #7 | How the COVID-19 pandemics increases plastic generation and dispersion

February 2, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-7-how-the-covid-19-pandemics-increases-plastic-generation-and-dispersion/>

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of plastics, as most protective and medical devices are, at least partially, made of it. At the same time, however, it has exacerbated the problem of plastic pollution due to the [increased production and dispersion](#) of protective devices, single-use plastics and plastic packaging in natural ecosystems. Moreover, the need for personal protective equipment has in some cases [led to the delay or withdraw](#) of national legislations against single-use plastic.

The relationship between COVID-19 and plastic generation and dispersal was already intuited at the beginning of the pandemic. Scientists are now beginning to quantify it: according to a [recent paper](#), as of August 2021, COVID-19 had led to the production of approximately 8.4 million tons of plastic globally; 25.9 thousand tons of which ended up in the sea. The research has also identified a dozen rivers that transported 79% of the COVID-19-generated plastic into the oceans.

These and future data are of foremost importance as they indicate critical points on which to act and to focus global efforts. In general, however, the authors conclude by reiterating the need already expressed by many experts: technologies to improve the collection, treatment and [#recycling](#) of plastic are urgently needed.

This is exactly our goal at MAELSTROM! The [innovative technologies](#) being developed by our consortium will contribute to improve the plastic management cycle by identifying and removing it from rivers and the seabed. Moreover, the recently launched MAELSTROM app will help operators to track the entire process, from litter identification up to its recycling outcomes. Environmental assessments and monitoring activities happening at the same time alongside the project will enable the identification of accumulation hotspots and will assess the impact of MAELSTROM technologies.

<p>COVID-19 has exacerbated the PROBLEM OF PLASTIC IN MARINE ECOSYSTEMS, increasing the PRODUCTION and DISPERSION of protective devices and packaging</p> <p>MAELDROPS #7</p>	
<p>This highlights once more the NEED TO PROMOTE TECHNOLOGIES to improve marine litter IDENTIFICATION, COLLECTION, TREATMENT and RECYCLING</p> <p>MAELDROPS #7</p>	

MAELDrop #8 | Studying marine litter from above with remote sensing

March 23, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-8/>

Understanding how much waste is present in the oceans, which trajectories it follows and where it accumulates is an essential step to understand its impacts on marine and coastal ecosystems and to set solutions to remove it. However, this is far from easy considering the vast ocean surface and the difficulty to physically access some areas. An important help in this sense comes from remote sensing technologies.

The [European Space Agency](#) (ESA) is funding 26 innovative projects to improve marine litter knowledge and monitoring [through remote sensing](#). Projects [cover different geographic areas and work on several fronts](#), including the development of new data processing, modelling and experimental techniques, mostly based on artificial intelligence.

MAELSTROM fully supports such initiatives. Even if our project works mainly “from the ground” we are convinced that the research activities supported by ESA will not only provide valuable information regarding litter accumulation hotspots on where to focus removal efforts, but they will also open the way to innovative ways to understand the quantities and dynamics of plastics in the environment and how they change in time. Two of MAELSTROM partners are involved in those ESA projects: CNR-ISMAR participates on the [TRACE](#) project, exploring the possibility to detect marine litter from satellite data and forecast their trajectories using a coupled system of water current forecast and marine litter dispersal model. Deltares, on the other hand, is leading the “Plastic Monitor” project, focused on the detection of floating plastic litter that is transported downstream, in very polluted rivers, such as the Citarum river, in Indonesia.

MONITORING THE VAST OCEAN surface to **UNDERSTAND MARINE LITTER QUANTITIES AND DYNAMICS** is not easy

An **IMPORTANT HELP** comes from **ESA** which is funding **MARINE LITTER PROJECTS** THROUGH **REMOTE SENSING**

MAELSTROM fully supports such initiative, as it will open the way to better **IDENTIFY ACCUMULATION HOTSPOTS**

And to better understand the **QUANTITIES AND DYNAMICS OF MARINE LITTER** in the environment and **HOW IT CHANGES IN TIME**

The infographic is divided into four quadrants. The top-left quadrant shows a blue sky over a calm ocean. The top-right quadrant shows a satellite in orbit above Earth. The bottom-left quadrant shows a cross-section of the ocean with a heatmap overlay. The bottom-right quadrant shows a large amount of marine litter floating on the water's surface.

MAELDrop #9 | Cetaceans, between yesterday's risks and today's risks

May 24, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-9-cetaceans-between-yesterdays-risks-and-todays-risks/>

Moby Dick classic novel presents a rich description of what was known about whaling and cetaceans at the time of author Herman Melville (1851); some of those descriptions may seem odd for a reader today! For example, Melville wrote that hunting sperm whales would not lead to the decline of their populations as species were considered to be immortal.

Unfortunately, the facts did not prove him right. In the XIX and XX centuries, when cetaceans were hunted mainly for their fat which would be transformed into oil (and that of sperm whales was particularly appreciated) and hunting techniques were refined, there was a sharp decline in cetacean populations. In order to protect those animals, in 1986, came into force the ban of the [International Whale Commission](#) (IWC), an intergovernmental body charged with the conservation of whales and the management of whaling. Some states, however, have continued whaling – no longer to obtain blubber from these cetaceans, but to trade their meat.

This activity is condemned by many quarters because it adds to the serious threats that cetaceans already face. A 2018 [report](#) signed by the Environmental International Agency and the Animal Welfare Institute states that human activities put cetaceans at risk both directly and indirectly, sometimes even acting synergistically: habitat degradation, chemical and noise pollution, unintentional entanglement in fishing gear result in a cumulative stress. Among those threats there is also, plastic pollution. According to the report plastic waste often traps animals or/ is ingested. In addition, baleen whales – cetaceans equipped with baleen to filter water – are also exposed to the risks associated with the ingestion of microplastics and associated pollutants.

In short, the activities of human species have created and still create severe damage to cetaceans. For this reason, MAELSTROM has chosen a cetacean as the “mascot” of its activities... a real-size model of a sperm whale calf, made entirely of recycled plastic which will accompany the MAELSTROM team during info days and clean-up activities, raising awareness among citizens on the risks that threaten marine ecosystems. The recycled material was kindly donated by the Italian [Ecopolyethylene Consortium](#). If you are in Venice or visiting the [Salone Nautico](#) come and visit us at CNR!

<p>PAST WHALING ACTIVITIES led to a STRONG DECLINE OF CETACEAN POPULATIONS. For this reason, IT HAS BEEN BANNED even if some States still practice it</p> <p>MAELDROPS #9</p>	
<p>That's why MAELSTROM has chosen a SPERM WHALE AS A PROJECT "MASCOT": it will accompany our teams on RAISING AWARENESS OF THE RISKS posed by plastics to coastal ecosystems</p> <p>MAELDROPS #9</p>	<p>Come and MEET OUR WHALE IN VENICE, during our NEXT WORKSHOP IN JUNE!</p> <p>VENICE JUNE 2022</p> <p>MAELDROPS #9</p>

MAELDrop #10 | Marine litter, a vehicle of transport for invasive species

September 2, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-10-marine-litter-a-vehicle-of-transport-for-invasive-species/>

When thinking of marine litter impacts on ecosystems, we often think about the ingestion and entanglement of animals. However, marine litter poses other lesser-known risks to ecosystems, such as the spread of invasive alien species. These are organisms that reach areas of the planet other than those where they are native and successfully establish there. Invasive species can bring in new pathogens and compete with native species for resources. In many cases, invasive species pose a serious threat to the conservation of species at risk of extinction: an example is the Louisiana red crayfish (*Procambarus clarkia*), which competes with the Italian crayfish (*Austropotamobius pallipes*), classified as endangered by IUCN.

How can marine litter contribute to the spread of invasive species? Several studies point out that litter, including microplastics, [act as transport platforms](#) for species, even over great distances. Other elements, such as boats (e.g., ballast waters), can harbour allochthonous organisms, but it is more difficult to quantify (and thus keep track of) organisms carried by litter.

It seems clear, however, that the problem is not limited. A [study](#) shows that floating plastic has allowed the introduction of alien species even in the Antarctic Peninsula, where temperatures were thought to be too freezing for organisms to survive (it is also worth considering how global warming [may reduce](#) this constraint). The Mediterranean basin is well studied for marine invasive species: according to a [JRC report](#), the more than 400 invasive species in the area arrived mainly from the Red Sea, via the Suez Canal, marine litter has been the vehicle for some of them.

In short, reducing the use of plastics, the main component of marine litter, and improving our litter management in general is crucial to protect aquatic ecosystems not always well-known ways! More needs to be done to inform citizens about all the implications of plastic consumerism and our MAELDrops aim at filling that gap!

The spread of **INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES** is one of the **LESSER-KNOWN RISK** posed by marine litter

We alien species are not from outer space... just from different areas of the planet!

Invasive species often **BRING PATHOGENS** and **COMPETE WITH NATIVE SPECIES** for resources

We can be animals, plants, even microorganisms... and it is not always easy to distinguish us from native species!

Marine litter act as **TRANSPORT PLATFORMS FOR INVASIVE SPECIES**, even over great distances

Not all of us manage to settle successfully in a new area. When we do it, we can become invasive!

Therefore, **REDUCING MARINE LITTER** is crucial **TO PROTECT ECOSYSTEMS** in several ways!

Eradicating us is not easy; better to avoid letting us in!

NO LITTERING

MAELDROPS #10

MAELDrop #11 | Bioplastics, biodegradable and compostable plastics: first episode October 20, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-11-bioplastics-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics-first-episode/>

As broadly known, plastics represent the main component of marine litter. Moreover, the current global plastic production is responsible for the [release of large amounts of CO2 emissions](#), which are fuelling climate crisis. Can then compostable, biodegradable and bioplastics be a sustainable alternative to traditional plastics? "Alternative plastics" present several environmental advantages, but they also pose important issues that need to be addressed according to their types.

The European Environment Agency [refers](#) to biodegradable plastics as being those materials which are capable of breaking down (biodegrading) under certain conditions and mediums; compostable plastics instead are those materials designed to biodegrade under the conditions of an industrial composting plant or industrial anaerobic digestion plant with a subsequent composting phase, or, at lower temperatures in the conditions of a well-managed home composter. On the other side, bioplastics are those made biomass sources (ex. food waste) as an alternative to petroleum. But beware, because not all bioplastics are biodegradable!

In fact, alternative plastics can take quite some time before fully degrade: a [study](#) conducted by researchers at the University of Plymouth showed that even plastics classified as compostable, while disappearing in water within three months, were still present in the soil after 27 months. Other materials tested, including a bag classified as biodegradable, remained intact in both water and soil after as much as 3 years! Anyway, times and efficiency of biodegradation depend on the kind of bioplastics and the environmental conditions.

This highlights one of the most important issues when talking about biodegradable, compostable and bioplastics: it is necessary to dispose them in the right way to ensure they can degrade without harming the environment.

The topic of bioplastics and compostable plastics is very broad, so we will talk more about it in the future. And remember: the best plastic will always be the one you don't use!

The infographic is divided into four quadrants, each with a different background color and text. Each quadrant features a central 'BIO PLASTIC' icon with arrows pointing to related concepts. The top-left quadrant (light blue) asks if bioplastics are a solution for marine litter and greenhouse emissions. The top-right quadrant (orange) lists advantages and important issues. The bottom-left quadrant (light green) discusses degradation periods and disposal procedures. The bottom-right quadrant (dark blue) emphasizes that the best plastic is the one not used.

Can COMPOSTABLE BIODEGRADABLE and BIOPLASTICS be a SOLUTION for MARINE LITTER and GREENHOUSE EMISSIONS related to plastic production?

These materials have many **ADVANTAGES** over traditional plastics - but they also pose **IMPORTANT ISSUES** that need to be addressed

Plastics labelled as compostable or biodegradable can take **LONG PERIODS TO DEGRADE** in natural conditions. Therefore, it is important to follow a correct **DISPOSAL PROCEDURE**

But remember: the **BEST PLASTIC** will always be the **ONE YOU DON'T USE!**

MAELDrop 12 | Let's de-plastify the Holidays!

December 12, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-12-lets-de-plastify-the-holidays/>

December means that holidays are coming! How can we make our celebrations plastic-free or at least plastic-less? In this month's MAELDrop we have collected some suggestions for you!

One of the most characteristic aspects of this time of the year are presents. Our suggestion is to opt for gifts based on experiences instead of material objects: a cooking class, a theatre yearly pass or a kayak weekend are all great opportunities to offer unforgettable moments to your loved ones. But if you need to go "material" look for eco-friendly options and objects that can be easily reused or recycled. Yes, unwrapping a gift is a wonderful experience! In this case consider using recycled or certified paper from sustainable sources, and avoid plastic ribbons, such as the traditional ones made of polypropylene.

Other wonderful moments of this time of the year are the big lunches and dinners with family and friends. During these occasions, we can still have the environment in mind by choosing washable or biodegradable crockery instead of disposable plastic plates and cups. The choice of food plays a vital role too: choose local food that can be transported in reusable or compostable bags and avoid global, packaged and high carbon footprint food.

Finally, decorations! There are plenty of alternatives to plastic and this also applies to Christmas tree lovers. Plastic trees have a strong environmental impact – just think about its production, transportation, and disposal! In case you don't feel like having a real tree, which is a better choice than a plastic one, you can think of artistic alternatives: your next Christmas tree can be made of cardboard, books, pieces of wood or wine corks!

Have a look at the links below for further tips, inspiration and ideas for a plastic-free holidays and impress your friends and family without the plastic!

- <https://www.wwf.org.uk/top-tips-sustainable-christmas>
- <https://theconversation.com/how-to-have-yourself-a-plastic-free-christmas-108828>
- Tree choice: <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-priorities/protect-water-and-land/land-and-water-stories/real-vs-fake-christmas-tree/#:~:text=Real%20or%20Fake%3A%20Which%20Christmas,you're%20actually%20supporting%20forests>

How can we make **OUR CELEBRATIONS PLASTIC-FREE**, or at least **PLASTIC-LESS**?

PRESENTS: CHOOSE EXPERIENCES and **ECO-FRIENDLY** objects. **BE AWARE OF PACKAGING** too

For family meetings **AROUND THE TABLE: GO LOCAL** with **FOOD** and opt for **WASHABLE CROCKERY**

PLASTIC DECORATIONS: find artistic alternatives using **NATURAL** and **EVERYDAY MATERIALS**. This year, impress your friends and family **WITHOUT THE PLASTIC**

MAELDrop 13 | An international treaty against plastic

January 17, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-13-an-international-treaty-against-plastic/>

An international and legally binding instrument to tackle the problem of plastic pollution: this is the [decision adopted](#) in March last year by the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA). It is a historic decision, involving all member states in the fight against plastics within a holistic approach that comprehends the entire cycle: from the extraction of fossil fuels for plastic production, to its disposal – that, as we have repeatedly said in our MAELDrops, often linger for very long times in ecosystems, damaging them.

This choice sends a strong message about the importance of international collaboration to address a problem that, as we know, ignores geopolitical boundaries. Beyond transportation and trade, in fact, plastic waste travels all over the globe carried by ocean currents.

The [first International Negotiating Committee](#) was held between November 28 and December 2022: more than 2,300 delegates from 160 countries attended the event which marks the first step in the development of the treaty (the deadline for negotiations has been set for the end of 2024). It will be a challenging work, not least because, as [some scientists point out](#), achieving the treaty will require accurate knowledge of where plastics come from, the trajectories they follow around the world, and according to which dynamics and responsibilities, requiring tremendous collaboration and good-will between science, policymakers, and citizenship.

As MAELSTROM, we strongly support the new treaty, wholeheartedly wishing the International Negotiating Committee and all the participating partners our best wishes. From our side we will keep contributing with our open data research and technological development to make the treaty effective on the shorter time possible!

March 2022: the United Nations Environment Assembly adopted a resolution to establish an **INTERNATIONAL AND LEGALLY BINDING TREATY TO TACKLE THE PLASTIC POLLUTION**

MAELDROPS #13

The treaty will address the **PROBLEM OF PLASTICS IN THEIR ENTIRE CYCLE** from fossil fuels **EXTRACTION** for their **PRODUCTION** to their **DISPOSAL**

MAELDROPS #13

The first **INTERNATIONAL NEGOTIATING COMMITTEE** was held at the end of 2022, between November 28 and December 2, marking an **IMPORTANT FIRST STEP**

MAELDROPS #13

As MAELSTROM, we **STRONGLY SUPPORT** the new treaty, contributing to make it effective on **THE SHORTER TIME POSSIBLE** by **SHARING OPEN DATA** on our research and technological developments!

#LetsDoItWorld

MAELDROPS #13

MAELDrop #14 | A new pathology: plasticosis

March 28, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-14-a-new-pathology-plasticosis/>

We have long discussed on the harms that plastics can cause to animals: whales found with stomachs full of plastic, birds imprisoned in remnants of netting and waste that prevent them from flying, reduced ability to feed and to reproduce, among several other consequences.

However, documenting "invisible" and sub-lethal effects of plastic ingestion outside laboratories is often challenging, making it difficult to prove the correlation of plastic ingestion and negative impacts on animal health. At least until a recent study, conducted on flesh-footed shearwater, a medium-sized seabird.

The authors [showed](#) that ingestion of micro- and macroplastics in this species results in an overproduction of scar tissue (i.e., fibrosis) in the digestive tract, more specifically in the proventriculus, where digestion takes place [1]. The greater the amount of plastic ingested, the worse the fibrosis [2].

Researchers have [named](#) this phenomenon "plasticosis," making it very clear how plastics can cause real pathologies – pathologies of the Anthropocene. In the shearwater, plasticosis can adversely affect the ability to absorb nutrients, the development of chicks, and make animals more vulnerable to infection. Moreover, although the research was conducted on only one species, it may affect others, and not just among birds.

Scientific evidence on the harms of plastics has long been too abundant to ignore. Action needs to be taken to substantially reduce pollution and to protect biodiversity. MAELSTROM deploys interdisciplinary expertise and new sustainable technologies to contribute to this goal, but a global challenge such as this, calls for a global collective effort. Stay with us; we will post regular updates on our work and suggestions on how you too can help!

<p>We already know that PLASTICS AFFECT ANIMAL well-being in many ways, but it can be challenging to study INVISIBLE AND SUB-LETHAL EFFECTS</p>	
<p>This phenomenon is called PLASTICOSIS and could also OCCUR IN OTHER SPECIES with, yet to discover, several other negative impacts</p>	

MAELDrop #15 | How old are microplastics in the sea?

June 20, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-15-how-old-are-microplastics-in-the-sea/>

How old are the microplastic fragments lying in our oceans? Knowing this can help us understand their origins and improve numerical models, used to determine the behaviour of plastics in the oceans. However, we still lack a method to accurately determine the age of microplastics.

A recent [study](#) proposes an interesting approach to estimate microplastics age. It is based on the analysis of polyethylene, one of the most common plastics (see our [MAELDrop 5!](#)), which degrades through environmental exposure. "This degradation level can be measured using the change in the material's molecular weight and something called the carbonyl index. Simply, when polyethylene degrades its carbonyl index increases and molecular weight decreases," says in a [release](#) the first author of the research, Rie Okubo.

Researchers conducted a series of experiments to understand how different combinations of temperature and UV radiation affected the degradation of polyethylene in order to standardize the degradation times. Once the degradation times were established, researchers conducted tests on microplastic samples collected from the sea, in the western North Pacific Ocean, finding that nearshore microplastics ranged from 0 to 5 years old, whereas offshore samples ranged from 1 to 3 years old.

Delving into the dynamics of plastics in the oceans is a key step in understanding how to reduce their presence and establish the most effective management policies. In the meantime, remember that we can all do our part daily by choosing products with as little plastic as possible and disposing of it properly so that it is directed to recycling!

Knowing the **AGE OF MICROPLASTIC** can be a valuable aid to understand their origins and to **IMPROVE NUMERICAL MODELING...**

However, we were still lacking a method **FOR PRECISE AGE DETERMINATION!** A recent study proposes a **NEW METHODOLOGY**

Based on the analysis of polyethylene, one of the most common plastics, researchers investigated **POLYETHYLENE DEGRADATION TIMES** based on **TEMPERATURE** and **UV RADIATION FACTORS**

Besides studies on plastic dynamics and management policies, remember that **EACH ONE OF US CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ITS REDUCTION,**

CHOOSING PRODUCTS WITH LITTLE OR NO PLASTIC and **DISPOSING OF IT PROPERLY!**

MAELDROPS #15

MAELDROPS #15

MAELDROPS #15

MAELDROPS #15

MAELDrop #16 | Oceanic birds and plastic exposure, a global assessment

July 20, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-16-oceanic-birds-and-plastic-exposure-a-global-assessment/>

We have repeatedly talked about the risks that marine litter, [particularly plastic litter](#), poses to animals. Unfortunately, new studies highlight even more of them.

A vast [research study](#) which brought together more than 200 authors from more than 160 institutes in various parts of the world presents the first global exposure assessment of seabirds (that is, species that live in the open sea), particularly petrel species to plastic litter. The researchers combined data on bird movements (analysing data from 148 populations in 27 countries and Antarctica) with data on plastic distribution: the main conclusion is that plastic hotspots are the areas most frequented by birds.

What does this mean? It means that the risk of plastic exposure for these animals is particularly high, even if it varies by species, population, and breeding season. This is particularly concerning if we consider that pelagic seabirds are already among the world's most endangered species groups – and the very species classified as "threatened" are also those for which exposure to plastic litter is greatest.

Researchers conclude their study by pointing out some of the priorities for species conservation and research, highlighting the key role of international cooperation as plastic pollution knows no borders, and marine litter travels throughout the seas, ignoring national boundaries. Another key message from researchers is the need to drastically reduce the quantity of plastics released into the environment. At MAELSTROM we certainly have no fear of repeating ourselves if, once again, we recall the importance of cutting the consumption of single use plastic and incentivizing a conscious and effective plastic management throughout its entire life cycle!

A new study highlights once again **THE RISKS THAT PLASTICS POSE TO ANIMALS.** It is the result of an extensive **INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH** that **BROUGHT TOGETHER SCIENTISTS** from more than **160 INSTITUTIONS**

Results show that **PLASTIC HOTSPOTS** in the sea correspond to the areas **MOST FREQUENTED BY PELAGIC SEABIRDS:** it means that for these species the risks associated with plastics are particularly high

We say it again: **PLASTICS HAVE NO BORDERS!** A drastic **REDUCTION** in their use, a proper **DISPOSAL** and management combined with international **COOPERATION**...

Are all critical elements if we are to truly **PROTECT THE ENVIRONMENT** we share with other species – **FOR THEIR AND OUR OWN WELLBEING!**

MAELDrop #17 | The approval of EU Nature Restoration Law

October 5, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-17-the-approval-of-eu-nature-restoration-law/>

After a break, our MAELDrops are back!

The summer brought us some really good news: in July the Nature Restoration Law [was approved!](#) The approval of this law represents a key step towards the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the EU Green Deal, by setting a binding legal framework for Member States to plan and achieve ecosystems' restoration targets.

The Nature Restoration Law sets as an overall target the restoration of at least 20% of the EU's land and marine areas by 2030 and ultimately all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. Specific marine targets [include](#) "the restoration of habitats in marine ecosystems".

It was not a foregone conclusion that the Nature Restoration Law would be passed! That is why at MAELSTROM we are celebrating its approval: environmental degradation, habitat and biodiversity loss, climate change and pollution are proceeding unabated, and the consequences are visible, undeniable and... scary! It is no longer time to procrastinate decisions, instead, we need politicians to make clear and decisive choices, recognizing the interdependence of human and natural well-being!

<p>In July, the EU PARLIAMENT APPROVED the NATURE RESTORATION LAW</p> <p>MAELDROPS #17</p>	
<p>Measures WILL COVER at least 20% of EU lands and SEAS by 2030</p> <p>MAELDROPS #17</p>	

MAELDrop #18 | The effects of plastics on human health

October 31, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-18-the-effects-of-plastics-on-human-health/>

In the last years research has increasingly highlighted the impacts of plastic pollution in ecosystems, especially marine ecosystems, but what about the effects on the human species?

#Plastics found in the oceans can reach our table, especially through the food web. According to several studies, humans ingest significant amounts of #microplastics on a daily basis: up to 5 grams per day, although estimates may vary. Microplastics can enter our bodies when we eat fish products in which it has accumulated but also through the breakdown of water bottles, by absorption of some cosmetic products and by air inhalation – just to mention some examples. Research over the years has shown the presence of microplastics in a variety of human tissues, including the placenta [1].

If it is truth that we increasingly know and understand more about the direct and indirect harms which plastics can cause to other species [2], things are less clear when it comes to our own. We know that plastic products are composed not only of the polymer that represents the actual plastic, but also of different types of chemicals that give it specific characteristics which can be toxic to living organisms, acting, for example, as endocrine disruptors (i.e., affecting the production of hormones). Recent studies have also shown how, due to their small size, microplastics can stress cell membranes, destabilizing them [3].

In short, as the World Health Organization reports [4], data are still scarce and there is much to be learned about the possible toxic effects of plastics on human health. However, its presence is ubiquitous, calling for more sustainable development models in which we can better use and manage plastics in our lives.

[1] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160412020322297>

[2] <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-14-a-new-pathology-plasticosis/>

[3] <https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.2104610118>

[4] <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/362049/9789240054608-eng.pdf?sequence=1>

<p>Research shows that we accumulate up to 5 GRAMS OF PLASTICS PER DAY IN OUR BODIES, but little is still known regarding the impacts of plastics on human health.</p> <p>MAELDROPS #18</p>	
<p>And that microplastics, due to their small size, COULD STRESS CELL MEMBRANES, destabilizing them.</p> <p>MAELDROPS #18</p>	

MAELDrop #19 | Plastic pollution is also an environmental justice issue

November 9, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-19-plastic-pollution-is-also-an-environmental-justice-issue/>

The environment and animal wellbeing are the most well-known victims of plastic pollution. But there are others, lesser-known victims of plastics. In fact, the impact of plastic pollution disproportionately affects the planet's most vulnerable communities, exacerbating socioeconomic inequalities globally. These are the main conclusions of a [report](#) published in 2021 by UNEP and the NGO Azul, which is dedicated to supporting grassroots communities to conserve marine resources.

The report documents the unfair effects of plastic at every stage of its life cycle: from the extraction of raw materials, leading to the destruction of habitats and the contamination of water and soil, to the production process, which often exposes those living near the industries not only to toxic chemicals but also, indirectly, to pollutants from, for example, trucks, and, of course, to the disposal phase. Inadequate plastic disposal, for instance, alters marine ecosystems, contributing to acidification and impacting the food chain—a detriment to the environment and to communities that rely on fish as their main source of protein.

As the report reminds, all these effects are exacerbated by the increased production and consumption of plastic [linked to the COVID-19 pandemic](#).

Plastic pollution is, in short, a real issue of environmental justice – one of the many. As Marce Gutiérrez-Graudiņš, co-author, of the report and founder and Executive Director of Azul, [says](#): "Plastic pollution is a social justice issue. Current efforts to manage and decrease plastic pollution are inadequate to address the full scope of problems it entails. Disparate impacts on communities affected by plastic, at every point from production to waste, should make environmental justice a customary consideration within the marine conservation field."

<p>Plastic pollution is not only a problem for the environment and animal wellbeing. It makes other less known victims!</p>	
<p>The effects have been exacerbated by the increased plastic production and consumption due to the COVID-19 pandemic</p>	

ANNEX 3 – Flash Interviews

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #1 | Talking about robotics and sustainability with Damien Sallé (Tecnalia)

March 9, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-1-talking-about-robotics-and-sustainability-with-damien-salle-tecnalia/>

Robotics is increasingly a part of scientific research in many fields. While it can be a concrete and valuable support for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals of the Agenda 2030, it also raises questions about its own sustainability: just think about the production of the necessary materials and their management.

These issues were recently discussed at the *What does it take for a robot to be sustainable?* conference organized by AI for Good, which was addressed by Damien Sallé, Coordinator of Robotics & Automation at our partner **Tecnalia** and one of the creators of our **Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform**. We therefore inaugurate with him our series of flash interviews, brief insights into the different issues we are facing in our MAELSTROM project!

Robotics and artificial intelligence are gathering enormous research efforts and appear to be increasingly important for our future. How can robotics and AI help us to achieve sustainable development models?

Indeed, robotics and AI are important technologies. They are used in more applications and sectors every day, not only in the manufacturing plants, but also in agriculture, health, construction, energy, logistics, inspection and maintenance and many more. In Tecnalia, for the past years, we are also developing a new line of applications targeting Environmental Sustainability and in particular the Circular Economy, because we also want to contribute to the fight against climate change. Robotics in this sector can help a lot to bring efficiency but also ensure quality, traceability and thus trust, which is a main barrier for a wider deployment of remanufactured or refurbished products.

We can see applications of robots in 4 main sectors:

- Removing the waste from the environment, like we do for the seabed marine litter in MAELSTROM
- Inspection and repair of equipment, using robots with vision to detect the defaults and additive manufacturing to repair them (works for plastics, metals, or concrete components)
- Dismantling, disassembling, and remanufacturing of equipment, to allow the re-use of some components or to remove as much pure material as possible before shredding and recycling. For example, we do that for electric car batteries or motors.
- Sorting the waste to increase the purity of the recycling processes, using robots with multispectral cameras and AI for example. It is already used in urban waste plants, and we develop solutions to expand it to construction waste, textile, batteries, RAEE etc.

Is there, conversely, any aspect of possible unsustainability coming from robotics and AI based technologies?

Well, robots are complex mechatronic machines. Therefore, they incorporate lots of metal, plastics, electronics, but also complex motors and gearboxes, complex sensors and many computers. More and more the AI runs not only on the robot embedded computer (edge) but also in the Cloud in powerful servers hosted in datacentres and communicating with the robot through internet. Most of the time they are electric machines, so mobile robots also need batteries. In some rare occasions where a very large autonomy is needed, they can be powered by a gasoline

generator. So yes, these machines have an environmental impact that is negative to build and operate them. Just like any other machine, I would say.

What can be done to prevent future robotic and AI technologies from reinforcing or creating “new” problems?

Everything in life is about balance... so technology itself is neither positive nor negative. It's how and why we use it that counts! Sustainability has three domains: economic, social, and environmental. In almost all cases, robots bring economic sustainability not only for the companies but also for the territories where they are deployed, because they allow a better competitive offer and allow maintaining a strong industrial ecosystem. They can also have an impact on the social domain when they are used to assist people with special needs in the workplace or help in ageing care for example. For environmental sustainability, we've already discussed some examples. Of course, selling useless robots for kids or geeks that end-up unused after a few days because they don't provide any real value, that is a very bad use of our resources and quota of CO₂... But it is not restricted to robots and apply to all our electronic devices, cars, fashion and so on.

If we focus on the environmental impact, and this is a personal opinion, in order to minimize the impact of the climate change on the ecosystems and biodiversity (reducing CO₂ emissions) I don't see other options than adopting sobriety practices which basically requires to do less. It means moving from a “consume-as-much-as-we-can” way of life to a “consume-wisely-and-only-when-needed” philosophy... Then we can work on optimizing the use of our quota of CO₂ to *Do Better* the products, technologies etc....

Given these premises, then, how can we minimize the environmental impact of robots?

Well, manufacturers could keep working on improving the intrinsic properties of robots, by using only recycled/recyclable materials, by optimizing their energy consumption, by optimizing their programming taking into account also energy parameters and so on.

But more critically: starting by using them only for things that are really worth the extra environmental cost! And for this, you enter in the evaluation of the sustainability balance, having to compare impacts of different natures: how can we decide if it is sustainable or not a robot such as ours in MAELSTROM, that requires CO₂ and materials for its manufacturing and operation, but have a positive impact on the environment because it removes pollutants? Well, there is a tool called Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) that lists all these positive and negative impacts throughout the

whole lifecycle of the system, from its design to its recycling. It's not easy nor perfect, but it is good indicator. I really encourage you to start using these tools to make informed decisions!

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #2 | Tackling litter in Venice Lagoon: Q&A with Fantina Madricardo

May 2, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/tackling-litter-in-venice-lagoon-qa-with-fantina-madricardo/>

In June, the MAELSTROM project will inaugurate its Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in Venice, an innovative technology designed to recover litter from the seabed (or lagoon-bed!) without damaging the ecosystems in which it operates.

The context in which we tested and where we will inaugurate the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform is not trivial. The Venice Lagoon, in fact, is not only the largest

lagoon in the Mediterranean but also gathers interests of different order, from naturalistic and ecological to economic and historical. What was it like, then, to set up the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in this specific context? We discuss this issue with Fantina Madricardo (CNR-ISMAR), coordinator of MAELSTROM.

Operating in the Venice Lagoon, even more with an ecologically friendly but sizeable and yet to be tested facility such as the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, is certainly not a simple process. What main factors did you have to consider?

First of all, it was necessary to identify the area both in the lagoon and at sea where the technology needed to be implemented to clean the environment, then we carried out a constant dialog with the local authorities in order to obtain their support and the needed permits to operate in the designated areas.

Much of the initial phases of MAELSTROM were devoted to studying the environment in which the technologies would work. In Venice, in particular, CNR-ISMAR carried out thorough litter assessment and mapping work: can you tell us the main results?

CNR-ISMAR started documented the presence of litter through high-resolution seafloor mapping, starting from a general survey carried out in 2013 of all the navigation channels of the lagoon, with specific repeated surveys in marine litter accumulation areas inside the Venice lagoon, close to the city of Venice. In the open sea, we mapped an abandoned aquaculture farm that will be the test site for the seabed cleaning platform at sea, following the indication and in full collaboration with the Venice Coast Guard. We found very high concentrations of litter in terms of number of items per sqkm, more in the lagoon than at sea. In the lagoon, we found mainly wrecks, tires, waste bags and litter related to the city, whereas at sea, we found mainly abandoned plastic ropes, nets and buoys related to fishing and aquaculture. To map the litter on the seafloor we used mainly high-resolution sonar (multibeam echosounder) and videos.

To conclude: did the preliminary investigations conducted prior to the installation of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform reveal any insights for future studies, or that made you think of other possible strategies to protect the Lagoon from litter?

Certainly, the maps of the litter distribution raise awareness in both citizen and local stakeholders about the presence of litter (otherwise invisible in the turbid waters) and the necessity to have a common strategy to clean the legacy of litter accumulated in the last decades in the Venice Lagoon.

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #3 | Marine litter and clean-up activities with citizens. A Q&A with Davide Poletto (VLPF)

July 13, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-3-marine-litter-and-clean-up-activities-with-citizens-a-qa-with-davide-poletto-vlpf/>

We are all part of this planet, and we can and should all know and care for it. Even European policies now **recognize** the crucial role of citizen involvement when it

comes to environmental issues and sustainable development: as members of society, consumers, voters... in every dimension of us, each one of us can play a relevant role in making change happen.

This also applies when it comes to marine litter and at MAELSTROM, we are convinced of the importance of raising awareness among civil society, seeing it as an active participant in the challenge of protecting the seas and oceans. For this reason, our project has foreseen regular info days and clean ups in Italy and Portugal (our pilot areas where our technologies will be implemented) **which represent moments** of dialog and interaction among science and society: our events are based on marine literacy, data sharing, ocean education and, above all, participation! In Italy, clean ups take place in Venice, home of our coordinator **CNR-ISMAR**, and are organized by our partner **Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF)**, in collaboration with various entities. We held **one just recently**, in June, which resulted in the collection of over 1,300 kilograms of waste in just one morning.

For our series of flash interviews, today we will delve into the topic of citizen participation and involvement and its importance on addressing environmental conservation challenges with Davide Poletto, director of VLPF.

When did Venice Lagoon Plastic Free start operating, and how did the idea come about?

Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF) was formally set out in the Spring of 2019. However, relevant board members were already active and engaged as practitioners and scientists in a broad array of sustainable development programs and projects. The idea came across after having engaged and mobilized multiple times local and international civil society organizations and citizens in marine litter clean up and monitoring sessions, also in cooperation with UNESCO. I am now the current director; I spent over one decade serving UNESCO in international scientific cooperation for sustainable development projects and programs. The idea of putting our activities in the world heritage site of "Venice and its lagoon" as a testing ground with a local and a global vision under a common roof was shared with colleagues and friends, who enthusiastically picked it up. VLPF was therefore set out and has made a good name herself. Since then, besides MAELSTROM, VLPF has been active in strategic lighthouse projects to *Restore our Ocean and waters* mission under the EU and in other independent and pioneer initiatives based on private donations and crowdfunding strategies such as the **"Ghost Boat" program**.

What is, in your opinion, the most important outcome of getting citizens involved in these types of activities (clean-ups)?

Clean-up and marine litter monitoring activities have several positive behavioural spillover effects by increasing awareness about the state of pollution of our shorelines and the level of dispersion of plastics in nature seas and waters. They can also contribute to providing helpful information to the local government and to the EU scientific database and network to fine-tune their marine litter prevention and remediation policies. Clean-up and marine litter monitoring activities bound us with our nature and biosphere, unleash and coalesce new energies to fight plastics pollution and advance towards the building of a new sustainable blue circular economy capable of operating with amending hands on this scourge, turning marine and waters wastes into new resources for our economies and services.

Observing how young generations are increasingly active about climate change, how would you classify the engagement of young generations in Venice regarding plastic pollution?

With a population below the threshold of 50.000 inhabitants in the historical city centre in a downtrend and an average age of about 50 years in an uptrend, Venice is a town facing social and demographic decay and impoverishment of its social tissue. We have a few organizations of youngsters active in the historical centre on the matter. Still, because of the shrinking and ageing population, they suffer from representativeness and poorness in social extraction and diversity. Transient populations, particularly students, are active and on the global wave of climate change protests and awareness campaigns are sensitive on the matter, advocating for more courageous and drastic changes in our economic development patterns locally and internationally. The number of associations and their activities in general is high, although sometimes too fragmented and conflicting.

What do you think could be improved in these kinds of actions? Are there aspects that could be enhanced, with the appropriate resources?

We believe that the town should be more courageous in carrying out the best course of action for sustainability. After the COVID-19 lockdown, we still see the pollution of our lagoon and shorelines rising up dramatically, as also underlined by our beach litter and water microcontaminants monitoring analysis. Public boats and private transport services for the public (taxis etc.) are still running on diesel fuel. The bottom of our lagoon is disseminated of tires of scrapped cars that are improperly used by transport boats as fenders. Thousands of them have piled up, increasing in number each day. The [MAELSTROM seabed cleaning platform](#) can represent a way to reduce such downstream pollution, but the solution is normative. Fiberglass boats are scattered and left like ghosts in our lagoon. The ghost boats issue is an unsolved

and escalating problem since proper disposal of small old boats and vessels unfit for navigation is unaddressed financially and regulatory. We need to create an economical chain capable of removing and segregating valuable materials – inox, aluminium, etc., and the final treatment of fiberglass, varnished woods, etc., through advanced recycling processes, free of charge for the citizens. Venice is part of the WWF Plastic Smart Cities initiative and has approved its implementation plan recently. We hope the above issues and many others that would be too long to mention will find an appropriate response in a reasonably short time span. Research institutes and NGOs cannot replace law and decision-makers. We can “only” inspire, catalyse, show new patterns and advocate for changes on scientific grounds and evidence.

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #4 | Discover the Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde

November 29, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-4-discover-the-bubble-barrier-vila-do-conde/>

On Saturday, November 25th, in Vila do Conde, Portugal, the launch event of our Bubble Barrier took place: an innovative technology for removing waste from rivers to prevent its entry into the sea and, consequently, accumulation in the oceans. This was a crucial moment for our project (there are many [photographic testimonials](#) on our social channels!), following the implementation of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform [launched in June 2023 in Venice](#). For its success, we truly must thank all the participants, and especially the [Vila do Conde Municipality](#) for their availability and for demonstrating so much proactivity in combating the problem of marine ecosystem pollution.

The Bubble Barrier system is designed not to disrupt fish or maritime traffic. It is co-powered by solar panels, designed and produced by the MAELSTROM partner [Institute for Sustainable Energy of the University of Malta](#), to ensure renewable energy. Furthermore, to ensure its sustainability, [CIIMAR](#), another partner of our project, conducted various environmental assessments.

The Bubble Barrier was developed by our Dutch partner, [The Great Bubble Barrier](#), so we ask them, for our *MAELSTROM's Flash Interviews*, to tell us how it works and explain some details!

What gave rise to the idea of a bubble barrier to stop litter in rivers? What was the inspiration for the development of this technology?

Three of the co-founders, Anne Marieke Eveleens, Francis Zoet and Saskia Studer, are lifelong sailors and friends who constantly came across plastic at sea on their sailing trips. When they were having a beer after one of their trips, they started mulling over ways to tackle plastic pollution. They dreamt of a solution that would target plastic but wouldn't hinder ship traffic or fish migration. The bubbles in their drinks eventually sparked their imagination, their concept and prototype were awarded and soon they started testing and developing their first prototypes further. At the same time, Philip Ehrhorn was developing his own Bubble Barrier in Germany. During a course in Environmental Engineering, he visited a wastewater treatment plant where he saw bubbles being used to aerate the water basin. The plastics that were flushed down the toilet, were pushed to the side of the basin. So, he wondered: 'Why can't we use the power of bubbles to capture plastic in rivers?' Eventually, the four of them met. They decided to join forces and together, they co-founded The Great Bubble Barrier.

How long will the barrier be maintained in the Ave River?

The Bubble Barrier system in Vila do Conde will be operational from the end of 2023. The team of engineers from The Great Bubble Barrier are responsible for adjusting the system so that it is optimally calibrated for the highest plastic catch possible.

The Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde is the first project in an estuary. The results of the pilot will be evaluated after 1 year of operation. With this project, we aim to realise a standard design for more estuaries in the future.

The Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde will be operational until at least the end of 2024, since the MAELSTROM project is executed within a limited time frame and aims to research long-term solutions, backed by research findings. The project focuses on research, which allows for 1 year of implementation, running and monitoring of the Bubble Barrier technology in this specific location.

The ultimate goal will always be to continuously capture and prevent marine litter, thus extending the Bubble Barrier project for a longer period of time in the Ave River. The Municipality will receive a report made by an independent auditor on the impact of the Bubble Barrier. If it is positive, the system will most likely remain in the water.

Of course, the Bubble Barrier is not the only possible tool to fight plastic pollution. Acting in synergy, various existing and/or developing technologies, including the Seabed Cleaning Platform developed within MAELSTROM, can help. But what specific characteristics might make the Bubble Barrier particularly suitable for a particular location? In other words, what characteristics of the river enable it to be successfully implemented?

The benefits of a Bubble Barrier are as follows:

- It covers the full width and depth of the river
- Ships can pass without obstruction
- It doesn't hinder the passage of fish or marine life
- The system can be operational 24/7

In addition, our Bubble Barrier system has been proven to catch 86% of debris –items ranging from 1mm to 1m in size.

Can you tell us something about the future prospects of your work? Is it possible (as well as desirable), for example, for the barrier to be implemented in other areas of the world?

The Great Bubble Barrier would like to see our Bubble Barrier technology implemented across the world. In the short term, we hope to implement more Bubble Barrier projects in Europe, and in the long term, we hope to implement projects in Asia and other continents across the globe.

MAELSTROM's flash interviews #5 | The environmental assessment of Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde: Q&A with Luis Vieira (CIIMAR)

December 7, 2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstroms-flash-interviews-5-maelstroms-flashinterviews-5-the-environmental-assessment-of-bubble-barrier-vila-do-conde-qa-with-luis-vieira-ciimar/>

We have talked extensively about the recently implemented Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde ([here](#) you can find our recent interview with the team from our partner, The Great Bubble Barrier, who developed it). However, the implementation of the system is only one part of the activities planned in our project: MAELSTROM aims to ensure the sustainability of its technologies, and thus, the project includes a thorough environmental assessment of their impact.

We discuss this with Luis Vieira from CIIMAR, the MAELSTROM partner responsible for the environmental assessment of the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River estuary.

What kind of environmental assessment will CIIMAR perform on the Bubble Barrier recently installed in the Ave River estuary? How do you determine the presence of macro- and micro-litter and what tools will you use to do this work?

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The CIIMAR team will be responsible for the environmental assessment of the Bubble Barrier on the Ave estuary. Conducting a thorough ecological assessment provides a comprehensive understanding of the estuarine ecosystem, its dynamics, and the potential impacts of litter, providing a foundation of knowledge essential for the effective implementation of a marine litter removal technology, also maximizing positive impacts and its efficiency. Several parameters were evaluated before the implementation of the Bubble Barrier. Macro-litter was quantified through visual monitoring during the ecosystem state assessment, whereas microplastic particles were evaluated in the water column. The presence of this debris was also co-monitored in key organisms, for example, zooplankton. The water quality and the ecosystem's ecological status were determined through standardized metrics, including the characterization of physical and chemical parameters, and analysis of biological and hydro-morphological elements.

With the Bubble Barrier now installed in the Ave estuary, this methodology will be replicated during the next months to evaluate its efficiency and impacts. CIIMAR team developed for the first time a hydrodynamic model for the Ave estuary. This model not only supports the technology implementation but will be also crucial to anticipate future scenarios and evaluate the Bubble Barrier efficiency.

Why it is important to develop this monitoring and litter removal in estuaries? What makes these areas important globally?

Rivers act as pipelines to the ocean, channelling the waste that is dumped into their waters and conducted to the estuaries and, finally, to the oceans. Thus, acquired data on the estuarine ecosystems can contribute to a better understanding of the entry of litter into the ocean from terrestrial sources. Estuaries support a complex web of life, including a diverse range of aquatic species. Marine litter can pose a threat to this biodiversity through entanglement, ingestion, and habitat degradation. To increase the knowledge on the contamination impacts on wild populations by both anthropogenic macrolitter and microplastics, more biomonitoring studies on those areas are still and urgently needed to support appropriate management measures. In addition, these field works are being considered crucial in the scope of national and international regulations.

Addressing marine litter in estuaries is essential for preserving the ecological integrity, economic functions, and cultural significance of these critical coastal ecosystems. Implementing removal technologies in these areas represents a proactive and targeted approach to mitigating the impacts of marine litter at the source, contributing to the overall health and sustainability of estuarine environments. It also provides an opportunity for community engagement and education. Local communities often have a vested interest in the health of estuarine ecosystems, and involvement in litter removal initiatives can raise awareness and foster a sense of environmental stewardship.

You also involve many different stakeholders in your project. Can you talk a little about who these stakeholders are and how you engage them?

No matter how innovative these technological solutions are, the mission to tackle marine litter will only be successful if we involve all sectors of society in a joint effort to change.

The CIIMAR team has been responsible for facilitating the involvement of local stakeholders in the co-design and implementation of the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde. Starting with the inspiring work with the municipality of Vila do Conde, which has taken a proactive approach to tackling marine litter by partnering with the MAELSTROM team to co-design and implement a Bubble Barrier in the Ave River. This technology was developed by [The Great Bubble Barrier](#), and it is co-powered through solar panels installed by the [Institute for Sustainable Energy](#) of the University of Malta. We also coordinated the involvement of local, regional and national stakeholders such as [Docapesca Portos e Lotas, S.A.](#), the [Portuguese Environmental Agency](#) as well as the [Vila do Conde Port Captaincy](#) and the Vila do Conde – [Environmental Monitoring and Interpretation Centre](#) (CMIA), which were extremely important for the design and implementation of the system.

CIIMAR had also an important role in stakeholder engagement at both national and international levels. The team will continue to be committed to contributing to awareness-raising efforts through strategic networking at national, European, and global levels, Science-Policy-Society interface activities and tools for citizen science. We developed an online interactive forum to encourage interactive thematic discussions. CIIMAR team also organized several international workshops, webinars and other online and presential events to inspire science and society to tackle marine litter.

We are proud of MAELSTROM's international dimension and recognition, with a particular emphasis on collaborative transdisciplinary actions that link science, industry, and policy. Recently, the project was highlighted as an example by the European Commission, which [awarded MAELSTROM the Atlantic Project Award](#) in the Healthy Oceans and Resilient Coasts category.

What kind of engagement activities have you done with the local community and are there more events planned for the future?

Citizen engagement initiatives have been crucial in mobilizing society to take proactive steps, raise awareness, contribute to data collection, influence policy, and foster a sense of shared responsibility for the health of the oceans. These initiatives followed the main MAELSTROM pillars, counting on vast support from national and local partners.

We believe that the first marine litter removal technology implemented in Portugal will inspire and mobilize society in the course of action for marine litter prevention and remediation policies, towards an effective and sustainable blue circular economy.

During the previous events, many of our participants asked for other initiatives, our team is already discussing the next project info days, capacity-building sessions on MAELSTROM's technologies, and out-of-the-box clean-ups. These will be key moments for awareness promotion on marine litter causes and impacts, promotion of good practices, and responsible choices and behaviours for a truly sustainable society.

ANNEX 4 – Newsletters

Newsletter #1

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

[View this email in your browser](#)

July, 2021

MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Welcome to MAELSTROM's project first newsletter! We are pleased to update you on the work we are carrying on, on our past and future events and all other news and milestones from the "MAELSTROM world". But, first of all... if you still don't know what MAELSTROM is about, let us introduce you the project!

What is MAELSTROM?

It is an EU-funded project designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments.

MAELSTROM will identify litter accumulation hotspots in the regions of Venice (Italy) and Porto (Portugal) and will implement two removal technologies - a **Bubble Barrier** and an **Underwater Cable Robot** designed to remove litter from the water column and from the sea/riverbed, respectively. Removal activities will be accompanied by environmental assessment, to understand the impact of marine litter in demo sites and that of the removal operations.

The removed litter will go through advanced recycling processes allowing for regenerated materials - such as polymers - to re-enter the industrial supply chains. At the end, feasibility studies regarding MAELSTROM's tested processes - from litter identification until its marketization - will bring together societal, economic and environmental indicators.

MAELSTROM will also contemplate science-policy interface, public awareness and societies' engagement regarding marine litter global challenge, through multiple events.

To know more, check our video [on YouTube](#) or [on our website!](#)

Our motto is:

Remove. Recycle. Give it a new use. Repeat

Will it be yours too?

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Who are we?

MAELSTROM brings together 14 international partners from 8 EU countries:

MAELSTROM's events

MAELSTROM's Kickoff meeting

Three days of intense work to present goals and activities to be carried out in the next four years. One common aim: **to protect coastal ecosystems** by identifying, removing, recycling, and putting marine litter back in the market chain: discover more about our kick off meeting, held in February 2021!

[Learn More](#)

With In-No-Plastic, our first international event

The workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities, held in Venice on June 3rd, was the first joint event of H2020 projects MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic. It was an **important moment to exchange knowledge** and updates on technologies being implemented for the removal and recycling of marine litter.

[Learn More](#)

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Our first joint clean-up campaign in Venice

Strong citizens' participation and **three tons of collected waste**: great achievements on our first MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic joint clean up which took place in Venice during the World Environment Day, on June 5th.

[Learn More](#)

Next step: Porto's clean up event

Alongside the **World Cleanup Day** we will have our next beach clean up happening in September. The event will be organized by our partner CIIMAR and it will take place in Porto (Portugal). Stay tuned through our website and social media to have more details in the following weeks!

[Learn More](#)

MAELSTROM's technologies

The Great Bubble Barrier

Between the 12th and 16th of April, CIIMAR hosted The Great Bubble Barrier team in Northern Portugal, where several estuaries were analyzed towards the implementation of the **Bubble Barrier**. Both parties worked together to identify areas where a major impact can be achieved regarding marine litter removal actions.

Parallely, and in order to learn how the Bubble Barrier functions under different conditions, Deltares conducted some tests in Amsterdam. Bubble Barrier Amsterdam is active since 2019 in one of the main waterways of the Dutch capital preventing plastics from flowing into the North Sea. Deltares' researchers measured the flow velocity through two means: one permanent system at one location and one moving system using a drone. They then analysed the litter collected on a daily basis to see how the amount and composition of waste collected vary with wind and flow conditions.

Some of the litter collected included food wrappers and even a few laminated restaurant menus, for which the source can easily be traced back. The test was conducted with tangerines, a common way to measure floating objects. Using this common method to monitor floating objects, they determined what fraction of the

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

tangerines was collected by the Bubble Barrier. The majority was forced to the side of the canal into the catchment system.

Through those tests Deltares and The Great Bubble Barrier teams are able to better understand how the Bubble Barrier will work under different conditions, which will be used to design and deploy the Bubble Barrier in Portugal.

Underwater cable robot

In the past 6 months, an intense activity has been going on between the partners involved in the design of the **robotic system** to remove the marine litter from the seabed (Tecnalia, LIRMM, STVenezia, CNR ISMAR, VLPP).

Environmental conditions of the Venice lagoon and its surrounding coastal area were evaluated, including depth, tide, currents on the surface and seabed, among others. Paralelly, information regarding the marine litter and plastics items that are expected to be found on the seabed were also collected, discussing it directly within local consortium's partners CNR- ISMAR and VLPP, as well as with other external partners. Technical requirements regarding the sensors to be integrated in the robot (cameras, DVL, IMU, GPS, ADCP etc.), have also been defined so that the latter can be teleoperated from the surface and, in the future, be autonomously piloted by artificial intelligence and automatic control software.

Based on all these requirements, Tecnalia has created different designs of the cable-driven parallel robot mechatronics structure, as well as designs of the robot end-effector that will include a dredge as suction device and an underwater gripper for the grasping of larger items. The optimization of the designs is close to be concluded so that manufacture can start shortly!

MAELSTROM's milestones

Identification of litter hotspot in Venice. CNR-ISMAR has been engaged in the identification marine litter accumulation hotspots in the Venice Lagoon and coastal areas, to identify the most suitable locations to implement MAELSTROM's removal technologies.

MAELSTROM's first field monitoring for stranded marine litter. Held on the last week end of April, this was the first joint activity for MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic, and the **beginning** of a series of monitoring actions regarding waste stranded along the coasts of the Venice Lagoon. This first assessment was moreover useful to collect ideas and suggestions for the setup of MAELSTROM's marine litter tracking app.

MAELSTROM goes *glocal*. Think globally, act locally: the Environmental Education Center of Cairo Montenotte, in Liguria (Italy), **has engaged some local schools to collect plastic** which will be recycled and processed to be build MAELSTROM's gadgets!

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MAELSTROM's networking

- [ITEM project](#)
- [EU Biovoices Project Conference](#)
- [BlueMed Conference](#)
- [Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul](#)
- [Chioggia Higher Education School & Fishermen Association](#)
- [European Maritime Day - Session BLUEINVEST](#)
- [NCR May Lecture - Netherlands Centre for River Studies](#)
- [EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with Marine Litter](#)
- [Quanta Eevent](#)
- [AreaAperta Primavera](#)
- [BleMed Hackathon 2021](#)

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Newsletter #2

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

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December, 2021

MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Welcome to MAELSTROM's second newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Environmental monitoring

Venice

In the last weeks, [CNR-ISMAR](#) started the environmental assessment in the Venice Lagoon by mapping hotspots of marine litter. CNR-ISMAR also tested different multibeam echosounder systems on the site to achieve the best results using the latest cutting-edge technology (Kongsberg, R2Sonic and Norbit). The maps will be the baseline of the next environmental assessment to be done before the robot implementation.

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

collected during the LIFE-LEMA project for analysis. Moreover, a large effort was done to define the complete robotic cell layout which is expected to be operational during the first semester of 2022 – on time to use the marine litter collected during the Venice summer clean-up on training the AI algorithm on real collected marine litter.

Main public events

In-No-Plastic/MAELSTROM workshop and Clean Up in Venice

The workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities*, the first international event of MAELSTROM and our twin project *In-No-Plastic*, was held in Venice on June 3rd. This was an important moment of knowledge exchange and an opportunity to share updates on recent technologies for the removal and recycling of marine litter. The workshop was followed by a Lagoon clean-up on June 5th, within the World Environment Day.

[Learn More](#)

Porto Clean Up and info day on World Clean Up Day

On the World Clean-up Day, held on September 18th, CIIMAR and CIMA Research Foundation partners have organized a beach Clean-up at Castelo do Queijo (Porto). The event was associated with an info day to raise awareness about marine litter related impacts, and it counted with a special guest: our sperm whale! A real-size calf installation entirely made of recycled plastic, that was possible due to the precious help of the Italian Ecopolietilene consortium.

[Learn More](#)

... Last but not least

MAELSTROM FIRST WEBINAR WITHIN THE OCEAN DECADE

Within the United Nations Ocean Decade Laboratories, under the call "A Clean Ocean," the MAELSTROM team organized a satellite activity on *Inspiring Science and Society to tackle Marine Litter*. The event was held on November 18th, 2021, during a one-day online seminar and saw the participation of fifty participants in representation of multiple sectors from academia, private sector, environmental NGOs and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). As for gender representation, 65% of the participants were women while 43% were men.

During the morning part of the webinar representatives of worldwide multi-scale marine litter initiatives presented the outcomes and the challenges experienced during their implementation efforts. On the afternoon, the webinar followed a participatory approach with discussions among panelists and participants on gaps and opportunities regarding marine litter within four clusters: i) Civic Engagement,

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Networking and Communication; ii) Stakeholder Coordination; iii) Governance; and iv) Funding

MAELSTROM APP

On December 11, a joint clean up event between MAELSTROM and the In-No-Plastics projects **closed the testing phase of the MAELSTROM app**. The App was designed to improve the marine litter collection and recycling processes based on more complete and accountable procedures. The App was developed by GEES recycling, ISD] and VLPE partners. Read more [here!](#)

JOINT STRATEGY

As part of WP 7, the MAELSTROM team CIMA and CIIMAR have developed a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter (ML) mitigation initiatives within the European space. The strategy aims at contributing to the **coordination and integration of blue technology for plastic strategy-oriented efforts** by directly collecting the perspectives of ML practitioners and stakeholders on current gaps in the field. It furthermore aims at identifying effective approaches for multi-level stakeholder engagement, hopefully leading to more effective policies and actions regarding marine litter reduction, identification, removal, and recycling. The document will soon be online on MAELSTROM's website!

WHAT'S NEXT?

2022 public event

Next year will take us to Venice (Italy), Porto (Portugal) and San Sebastian (Spain) for more clean ups and info days: stay tuned on our website and social media for updates!

Next webinars

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Not only public events: in 2022, we will organize two more webinars regarding marine litter and its challenges, so to increase networking actions across public, private, and societal actors also making use of our Forum: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/forums/forum/maelstrom-forum/>

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

June

- 01: [EU Cluster meeting in project dealing with Marine Litter](#)
- 08: [Quantia](#)
- 16: [Area Aperta](#)

- 17: [BlueMed Hackathon](#)

July

- 08: [EMBA2021 Marine Robotics](#)

September

- 12: [Quantia](#)
- 14: [BlueMed Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Ma](#)
- 23: [Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS"](#)

October

- 26/27 [Ecomonda](#)

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Newsletter #3

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #3

18/12/23, 08:51

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June, 2022

MAELSTROM Newsletter #3

Welcome to MAELSTROM's third newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

In February 2022, MAELSTROM's partners had a General Assembly and shared the main results of the first year of project. A quick update:

- **Characterization of major sources of marine litter in Venice and Vila do Conde.** MAELSTROM's leader [CNR-ISMAR](#) performed a systematic analysis and characterization of the marine litter sources in the northwestern Adriatic Sea and northwestern Portuguese coast and estuaries
- **Preliminary study assessment of the surface/water column Cleaning Device in the Netherlands.** Our partner [Deltares](#) carried out a one-week measurement campaign to understand how efficiently the Bubble Barrier is working in Amsterdam
- **Identification of the site for the installation of the Bubble Barrier.** Taking in consideration different aspects, [CIIMAR](#) and [The Great Bubble Barrier](#) identified the most suitable area of installation of the Bubble Barrier in Portugal
- **Integrated feasibility assessment report for the implementation of the MAELSTROM Bubble Barrier in Portugal.** Following the assessment of technical, practical, financial and environmental impacts, The Great Bubble Barrier has designed a suitable configuration of the Bubble Barrier and its solar panels, ensuring a maximized efficiency within the river's catchment system
- **Operationalisation of the MAELSTROM App.** Our partner [GEES](#) and [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#) have designed and developed complete hardware and software systems for marine litter identification, tracking and monitoring, following international standards of codification of marine litter items

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- **Communication.** Our partner CIMA produced a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding marine litter mitigation, removal and recycling initiatives worldwide. Moreover, **CIMA** produced the MAELSTROM's Dissemination and Communication Plan; an interim report will be delivered by the end of June 2022

Find out more [here!](#)

MAELSTROM technologies

In June, our partners **Tecnalía** and CNRS-LIRMM have tested successfully the **Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform** that is soon to be installed in the Venice Lagoon.

While waiting for the transfer of the platform to Venice and in order to support its installation, CNR-ISMAR team collected videos and data, using a multibeam echo sounder and a miniROV, in the marine litter hotspots previously identified in the Venice Lagoon.

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18/12/23, 08:51

Understanding that MAELSTROM's technologies are too big to be transported, we have created two mini technologies to take with us to events and conferences! In the pictures below, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform scale model (about 4% of the size of the real platform) exposed during the [Venice Boat Show](#) and the Bubble Barrier scale model presented during the [UN Ocean Conference](#).

Main events

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EU Green week

Within the EU Green Week 2022, MAELSTROM team organized **three events**:

- May 31 - **meeting with local stakeholders**, to highlight the current marine litter management system in Venice in light of the recent approval of the Italian Salvamare regulation, which marks a turning point for the circular economy of marine litter in Italy. Activities and efforts of various European projects have been presented, each supporting the technological and cultural step needed towards sustainable marine litter management in Italy and across Europe.
- June 1 - **International workshop Removal of Marine Litter and the Circular Economy – Challenges and Opportunities**, second edition of our annual workshop jointly organized with our twin project **In-No-Plastic**. The workshop presented innovative and sustainable technologies for the removal and recycling of marine litter creating a chance for large industrial entities, start-ups, and NGOs to meet, exchange ideas, and to create synergies. The workshop was held at the Venice Boats Show and, at the CNR-ISMAR stand, we could also present our mascot, the calf sperm whale realized with recycled plastic kindly donated by the Italian Ecopolyethylene Consortium.
- June 2 - **Venice clean-up event**. In collaboration with In-No-Plastic, MAELSTROM organized a clean-up event in Venice and in the small islands at the lagoon outskirts. During the clean-up, the MAELSTROM App, now completely operational, has been widely used by MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic consortiums, local environmental associations, and volunteers. A total of 1734,36 Kg of litter was collected in just a couple of hours!

More information [here!](#)

Our calf sperm whale model at CNR-ISMAR headquarters during the Venice Boats Show. Another whale is exposed in Portugal, at CIIMAR's headquarters

MAELSTROM's webinars

On May 10, we held our second webinar untitled *Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud*, together with In-No-Plastic and [RELIANCE](#) projects.

The webinar, addressed to the scientific marine litter community, presented operational tools to produce collaborative scientific work on Marine Litter pollution using the EOSC digital services.

Flash news

UN Ocean Conference 2022

We have been honoured to participate at the [UN Ocean Conference 2022](#), which took place at the end of June in Lisbon! Besides participating at the Conference, MAELSTROM was also present at three side events:

- *Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event* – June 25, Matosinhos
- *One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Even* - June 28, Lisbon
- *EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action* - June 29, Cascais

Other interesting events took place during the first six months of 2022, providing a fantastic opportunity to highlight MAELSTROM and to connect and network with other colleagues internationally. Just to name a few:

- **Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments**
- **Expo Dubai - Land - City - Sea - Scape Intelligence Multidisciplinary and Systemic Approaches for the Rational Use of Resource and Sustainability**
- **GEOHABB 2022** – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping
- **EMRA 2022** - Workshop European Marine Robotics & Applications Workshop
- **AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS** (within BIEMH22 trade fair)
- **ERF2022 – European Robotics Forum** – Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop

A study in the vertical distribution of litter in rivers

Rivers play an important role as ecosystems, supporting the lives of many species, and for human activities. Unfortunately, they also act as a road that allows litter to reach the sea.

MAELSTROM Newsletter #3

18/12/23, 08:51

We still know relatively little, however, about how litter - and in particular plastic, the most represented in the sea - is distributed in the water column. Most studies, in fact, have focused on litter visible to the eye in the surface layers: but can we say there is as much of it in the depths?

A recent [paper](#) by Elise Blondel from Allseas and Frans Buschman from MAELSTROM's partner Deltares begins to answer this question. Their results show that the concentration of plastic near the riverbed is similar to that in the more superficial layers of the water column.

"This plastic adds to the plastics transport to the sea. Since the flux lower in the water column is substantial (at least for the investigated location, but it was also found in other Dutch locations), it should be taken into account", says Dr. Buschman.

Read more [here!](#)

Don't miss our MAELDrops!

We are producing a set of MAELDrops, "pills" of information about marine litter, the danger it poses to ecosystems, and possible management strategies. Find them on social media channels by searching for [#MAELDrops](#) or read them directly on our website on the [news page!](#)

Our motto is:

Remove. Recycle. Give it a new use. Repeat

Will it be yours too?

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Newsletter #4

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #4

17/12/23, 00:08

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December, 2022

MAELSTROM Newsletter #4

Welcome to MAELSTROM's third newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Almost halfway into MAELSTROM!

We are now carrying out the third of a total of six phases: 1 – Localize; 2 – Characterize; 3 – Collect (we are here!); 4 – Sort; 5 – Transform; 6 – Marketize.

A lot still needs to be done to achieve our goals but end of the year newsletters are a good moment to celebrate our latest achievements. While we leave you to read, we take the chance to wish you a wonderful Holiday period and to thank you for being part of MAELSTROM with us! See you in 2023 with a renovated enthusiasm to beat plastic pollution!

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HIGHLIGHTS

- **Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters 2030**

We are happy to share that **MAELSTROM has joined the European Commission's Charter of the Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters 2030**. MAELSTROM supports the Mission in several ways, by acting on the protection of aquatic ecosystems and on pollution prevention through its innovative marine litter removal and recycling technologies. The call is open to a wide audience of stakeholders and aims to give a clear signal of the importance of protecting inland waters and oceans by taking concrete actions. [Here](#) you can find more information on the Mission and how MAELSTROM supports it!

- **Seabed Cleaning Platform tested in Venice**

Important progresses were made on assembling our **Seabed Cleaning Platform based on Robotics**: the system was designed and produced by our partners [Tecnalia](#), [CNRS-LIRMM](#) and

[SI](#) and tested in the Venice Lagoon during last September. We weren't the only ones being enthusiastic about it: also the President of the Veneto's Region, Mr. Luca Zaia, understood the usefulness of our Platform, as you can see in this [viral post](#), proving that local stakeholders can be actively engaged in common-good solutions. Have a look at the video produced by our partner Tecnalia to understand how the Platform works [here](#).

- **How good is it?**
Cleaning operations in Venice were accompanied by our partner and project coordinator [CNR-ISMAR](#) which has conducted several **environmental monitoring**

actions in the areas where the Seabed Cleaning Platform operated: the aim is to document the removal of marine litter in those areas confronting data from before and after the cleaning operations and to understand if and how the environment is changing after such actions. Find out more [here](#).

- **World Clean Up Day**

On September 17, as part of the [World Clean Up Day](#), we had our yearly multidisciplinary beach cleanup in the city of Vila do Conde (Portugal). The event was organized by our partners [CIIMAR](#) and [The Great Bubble Barrier](#), in collaboration with the [Centro de Monitorização e Interpretação Ambiental](#) (CMIA) and the [Câmara Municipal de Vila do Conde](#) and supported by [Lipor](#) (Intermunicipal Waste Management Service of Greater Porto) and [Unifardas SA](#). See some pictures [here](#)!

- **Bubble Barrier @ Portugal**

We are looking forward to launching the first Bubble Barrier in Portugal! After some unexpected delays we are now finalizing the last technical issues to be ready to deploy this innovative litter removal system in Vila do Conde in 2023. Stay tuned for more information!

- **Earthshot Prize 2022**

By the way: our partner [The Great Bubble Barrier](#) was nominated as one of the finalists for the [Earthshot Prize 2022](#), the world's most prestigious and ambitious

environmental prize, in the category *Revive our Oceans!* They haven't won the Prize, but they have not lost either...you can never lose when your mission is to protect the environment! Congratulations to all the nominees and a special high five to our Dutch partners!

• **MAELSTROM APP**

We had a chat with Giorgio Betteto, from our partner [GEES Recycling](#), and Martina Bocci, from our partner [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#), both in charge of the development of the MAELSTROM App, to learn more about its main features and how it can be of support for marine litter practitioners. [Here is the interview](#); and if you want to learn more about our App, have a look at our [new video](#)!

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

- [Pan-European digital assets supporting research communities – Benefits & Opportunities](#)
- [Innovazul 2nd International Meeting on Knowledge and the Blue Economy](#) - Open Innovation Session
- [Black Sea CONNECT Marine Litter Action Forum](#)
- [MARELESS](#) Marine Litter and Circular Economy, by [Interreg Italy-Croatia Programme](#)
- [European Research and Innovation Days 2022](#) - session Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters: synergies and next steps

LAST BUT NOT LEAST: FOLLOW US AND DON'T MISS OUR #MAELDROPS!

This [month's MAELDrop](#) is about having a plastic-free Holidays with family and friends. Have a look at the suggestions that we have collected for you and follow us on social media to be always updated on the next MAELSTROM's milestones.

Our motto is:

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Will it be yours too?

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Newsletter #5

<https://us6.campaign-archive.com/?u=29f791f69e98ddd6bbc588e28&id=501cd94ac4>

MAELSTROM Newsletter #5

17/12/23, 00:08

[View this email in your browser](#)

June, 2023

MAELSTROM Newsletter #5

Welcome to MAELSTROM's fifth newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Launch of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform

These last six months were extremely interesting for MAELSTROM! While activities keep being developed by all partners a special highlight goes to partners [Tecnalia](#), [CNRS-LIRMM](#) and [ST-Servizi Tecnici](#) which have finalized the testing phase of MAELSTROM's Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform - an innovative technological system for marine litter removal based on AI to sustainably remove litter from the seabed, without harming ecosystems. After being tested in Venice in September 2022, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was officially inaugurated on June the 9th, as part of the [European Green Week](#) and at the presence of Venice's councilor for the environment Massimiliano De Martin. Do you still remember how it works? If not, check [our video](#).

Click [here](#) to know more about the event.

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Third International Workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economic: Challenges and Opportunities*

June was also the month for our Third International Workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economic: Challenges and Opportunities*, organized in collaboration with our twin project [In-No-Plastic](#) as a side event of the [Venice Boat Show](#). The meeting, which took place on June 1st at the headquarters of CNR-ISMAR, gathered representatives from academia, industry, and society to discuss the state of the art on knowledge and tools to monitor, remove and recycle marine litter, thus contributing to the achievement of the [EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters](#). However, as you know, we do not stop at meetings and workshops! The day after, thanks to our partner [Venice Lagoon Plastic Free](#), in collaboration with [WWF Plastic Smart Cities program](#), the [Italian Red Cross](#) and [Fare Verde](#) and [Poseidon](#) associations, we have organized a cleanup of the Venice canals and surrounding islands.

Cleanup activities are extremely important for MAELSTROM as they allow us engage citizens in the challenge of marine litter reduction and ecosystem protection. It never ceases to amaze us how much waste can be collected during these events: in just one morning our volunteers collected more than 1,300 kilograms of waste! The waste collected was identified and reported with the MAELSTROM App - developed according to the [EMODnet](#) categories- and sent to our partners [GEES](#) and [MAKEEN](#) for recycling.

Read more [here](#).

EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters – The Mediterranean Lighthouse in Action

Our project coordinator Fantina Madricardo from [CNR-ISMAR](#), and our colleagues Isabel

<https://mailchi.mp/0fc2aa8fb7e1/maelstrom-newsletter-8125591?e=b2a937ccb4>

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #5

17/12/23, 00:08

Sousa Pinto and Luis Viera from [CIIMAR](#) participated at the *EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters* held in Palermo on May 30-1. They have represented MAELSTROM at the [Blue Mission Med](#) 1st Mediterranean Stakeholder Forum, under the Research & Education Table, in two sessions:

- Inspire and Inform: where they have showcased MAELSTROM's main achievements in [#research](#), [#oceanliteracy](#) and [#socialengagement](#).
- Blue Mission Med Stakeholder Forum: a session designed to identify key aspects towards implementing the Mission Lighthouse and to elaborate concrete actions (what and how) for each category.

MAELSTROM's WHALE - guest at CNR Anthropocene exhibit

Our third sperm whale, made of recycled polyethylene kindly provided by [Consorzio Ecopolietilene](#) is a special "guest" of *Anthropocene*, an exhibit celebrating the 100 years of the Italian Science Research Council (CNR). MAELSTROM's whale draws attention to the impacts of plastic pollution to marine ecosystems and it will be displayed at Palazzina Canonica, historical headquarters of [CNR-ISMAR](#) in Venice until July the 5th. If you happen to be in Venice during the next weeks, do not miss the opportunity to see the exhibit!

More info: <https://antropocene.cnr.it/>

<https://mailchi.mp/0fc2aa8fb7e1/maelstrom-newsletter-8125591?e=b2a937ccb4>

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World's Biggest Butt Pick Up - 1 million cigarette butts / Clean up in Vila do Conde

Between March and April, our team has dedicated specific efforts to the schools of Vila do Conde - our pilot location in Portugal. Our colleague Luis Vieira from [CIIMAR](#) gave some hours of training, during which he presented MAELSTROM's mission and goals, showing students the MAELSTROM App and a mini prototype of the Bubble Barrier, soon to be installed in the town's Ave River. On April 19th a joint clean up with students from Agrupamento de Escolas Dr Carlos Pinto Ferreira, in collaboration with CIIMAR and [CMIA](#) was organized at Ave's Estuarine Beach. During the cleanup students collected both macro- and microplastics and lots of cigarette butts! They have then decided to participate at the [World's Biggest Butt Pick Up - 1 million cigarette butts challenge](#), a national challenge launched by environmental activist The Trash Traveler. It was such a fun and enriching experience for all!

MAELSTROM's stakeholder meeting in Vila do Conde, Portugal

On April 4th, part of the MAELSTROM's Consortium has gathered in Portugal with national stakeholders from the [Vila do Conde Municipality](#), the Portuguese Secretary of State for Fisheries, the [Portuguese Environment Agency](#), the National Maritime Authority-Captaincy of Vila do Conde and [Docapesca](#) to share and discuss MAELSTROM's activities and goals for the

region. The meeting, held at the Environmental Monitoring and Interpretation Center (CMIA) was an important occasion to collect and align stakeholders' needs and suggestions regarding the implementation of a [Bubble Barrier](#) in the Ave River. Challenges, opportunities, and next steps for the installation of the system were widely discussed, ending with a unanimous and positive consensus for its local implementation and maximization.

MAELSTROM 5th General Assembly and Steering Committee

On February 15th and 16th, we had our 5th General Assembly and Steering Committee, hosted at [CNRS-LIRMM](#) headquarters in Montpellier. As we enter the second biennium of our project, we have spent those two days sharing lessons learned - what is working well, what is not? Which are the future challenges and opportunities for MAELSTROM's findings? There is a lot we can learn from each other and from difficulties and at MAELSTROM real sustainability starts with facing problems with an honest approach and working together to find solutions!

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

- [European Maritime Day](#) & Kick Off Meeting of the EU funded [WINBLUE Project - Empowering Women and Mainstreaming Gender Equality in the Blue Economy](#)
- [GeoHab International Symposium](#)
- CINEA Workshop [Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects](#)
- [14th European Robotics Forum](#)
- [AI for Good - What does it take for a robot to be sustainable?](#) conference
- First [EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters](#) Forum
- Air Centre Friday Networking online seminar [Marine Litter and Biodiversity: Co-Detection and Impacts](#)

WHAT'S NEXT?

Huge expectations for the next months as we will be implementing our second marine litter removal technology - a [Bubble Barrier](#), developed by our partner [The Great Bubble Barrier](#)! The Ave River in the Portuguese town of Vila do Conde was the place chosen to deploy this smart technology for plastic pollution. The system uses a bubble curtain to capture plastic pollution in rivers and, in the case of MAELSTROM, it will be co-powered by solar energy through our partner [Institute for Sustainable Energy - University of Malta](#). After some delays,

a launch event is now foreseen to happen between September/October 2023. Our local partner **CIIMAR** is on the spot making sure all will happen smoothly, so fingers crossed and be tuned for more information soon!

Credit: courtesy of The Great Bubble Barrier

LAST BUT NOT LEAST: FOLLOW US AND DON'T MISS OUR #MAELDROPS AND FLASH INTERVIEWS!

This **month's MAELDrop** is a study to estimate the age of microplastics in the sea. Why it is important to know, and which innovative approach is under discussion? Follow us on social media to be always updated on our MAELDrops and MAELSTROM's main milestones!

We are also glad to announce that MAELSTROM's communication group has started a new editorial project called **MAELSTROM's flash interviews**. Alongside our MAELDROPS, they attempt to be an informative tool to deepen some aspects of partners' work which might not come across immediately. What is the link between robotics and sustainability? How are bathymetric maps useful to remove waste from the Venice Lagoon? What is the role, and which are the challenges for citizen's engagement in addressing marine litter?

MAELSTROM flash interviews are a series of short interviews with our partners, you can find them on social media but also on our website. Here the first two. Enjoy the reading!

- [MAELSTROM's flash interviews #1 | Talking about robotics and sustainability with Damien Sallé \(Tecnalia\)](#)
- [MAELSTROM's flash interviews #2 | Tackling litter in Venice Lagoon: Q&A with Fantina](#)

MAELSTROM Newsletter #5

17/12/23, 00:08

[Madricardo](#)

Our motto is:

Remove. Recycle. Give it a new use. Repeat

Will it be yours too?

Co-funded by
the European Union

<https://mailchi.mp/0fc2aa8fb7e1/maelstrom-newsletter-8125591?e=b2a937ccb4>

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ANNEX 5 – MAELSTROM Events

- MAELSTROM Kick off meeting, February 3-5, 2021, Online | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/eu-h2020-maelstrom-kicks-off-to-tackle-marine-litter-in-coastal-ecosystems/>

- 1st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities – June 3, 2021, Venice, Italy | Joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/maelstrom-in-no-plastic-workshop/>

- Clean up Venice; Italy – International Environment Day within the EU Green Week, June 5, 2021 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/maelstrom-in-no-plastic-workshop/>

- Clean up Porto, Portugal – World Clean Up Day, September 18, 2021 <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/beach-clean-up-2/>

- Webinar: *Science and society: Working together to address the marine litter challenge*, November 18, 2021 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/inspiring-science-and-society-to-tackle-marine-litter/>

- Webinar: *Localize and Characterize: Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services*, May 10, 2022

- Local Stakeholder meeting & Demonstration event - Venice | May 31, 2022 | Within the International Venice Boat Show | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/inspiring-science-and-society-to-tackle-marine-litter/>

- 2nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities – June 1, 2022, Venice, Italy | Joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project

- MAELSTROM Clean-up Venice – International Environment Day within the EU Green Week, June 2, 2022 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/venice-clean-up-2022/>

- Beach clean-up Vila do Conde 2022 | World Clean-up Day, 17/09/2022 <https://www.facebook.com/ciimar.up.pt/photos/a.452642448081643/5852906228055211/>

- Marine Biodiversity Networking Fridays | Webinar Biodiversity and Marine Litter: co detection and impacts, 10/02/2023
<https://www.aircentre.org/netfridays-marine-biodiversity-11/>

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/webinar-marine-litter-and-biodiversity-co-detection-and-impacts/>

- Third International Workshop on Marine Litter Monitoring, Removal and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities, 01/06/2023 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/third-edition-of-the-international-workshop-removal-of-marine-litter-and-circular-economic-challenges-and-opportunities/>

- Live demonstration Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, 9/06/2023 – EU Green Week

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/live-demonstration-of-the-robotic-seabed-cleaning-platform-in-the-venice-lagoon/>

- Sunset Beach Clean-up Vila do Conde, 16/09/2023 – World Clean-up Day and EU Act Now Campaign | *Event postponed from the 16th to the 23rd due to weather conditions*

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstrom-sunset-beach-cleanup-vila-do-conde/>

The poster is for a 'Sunset Beach Cleanup' event. At the top, it features logos for the European Union, ACTNOW, MAELSTROM (with the tagline 'Smart technology for Marine Litter Sustainability Remediation and Management'), and World Cleanup Day. The event is scheduled for September 23rd in Vila do Conde. The program includes: 17h00 - Reception and briefing; 17h30 - Start of beach cleanup; 19h00 - Lunch break; 20h00 - 'Lixo Marinho e Microplásticos' activities; 21h00 - Cosmic walk; 23h00 - Event end. Registration is open, with a QR code provided. The meeting point is at CMIA - Vila do Conde (41°20'39.6"N, 8°44'44.0"W). The organizing partners are ciimar, Câmara Municipal Vila do Conde, counting stars, and the environmental monitoring center. Support is provided by DOCAPECA, Águas do Norte, FOCA, UNIFARDAS, and the European Union.

- Launch event Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde, 25/11/2023

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/european-project-maelstrom-launches-a-bubble-barrier-in-portugal-to-catch-plastic-in-the-ave-river-at-vila-do-conde/>

ANNEX 6 – External events

YEAR 2021

- ITEM project online workshop, 13/01/2021
- EU Biovoices Project Conference, 14/01/2021

- Blue Med Final Conference, 22-23-24/02/2021

<http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/bluedmed-final-conference/>

- **Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul, 23/04/2021** | <https://ambienteportugal.pt/event/ecossistemas-marinhos-e-economia-azul>

- **European Maritime Day - Session BLUINVEST, 21/05/2021**

https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/2021-european-maritime-day-2021-05-20_en

- NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies, 26/05/2021
<https://ncr-web.org/events/ncr-may-lecture/>

NCR May Lecture
26 May 2021 - 13:00

Netherlands Centre for River studies **NCR | May Lecture**

Date 26 May, 2021 | 13:00 - 14:00
Lecturer Frans Buschman
Topic Transport and fate of plastic litter in rivers - how can monitoring be supported by modelling?

- EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter', 01/06/2021

<https://bioplasticseurope.eu/media/pages/news-events/horizon-2020-cluster-meeting-on-marine-litter/21c23f102f-1646989939/agenda.pdf>

- Venice International Boat Show, 29/05/2021 - 6/06/2021
<https://salonenautico.venezia.it/eventi/removal-of-marine-litter-and-circular-economy-challenges-and-opportunities/>

- Online seminar in the framework of the event "Arazzi del Mare", 8 /06/2021
- AreaAperta Primavera, 16/06/2021

- BlueMed Hackathon 2021, 17/06/2021

- EMRA2021 Robotics, 08/07/2021

- BlueMed - Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter, 14/09/2021

Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter

September 14, 2021, CNR ISMAR in Venice and online

This workshop looks at the most promising R&I solutions undertaken, as well as the policy instruments implemented, in the management and valorization of plastic litter in Ports/Harbours and their hinterland at Mediterranean level. The aim of the event is to identify gaps and bottlenecks to be overcome for an effective prevention and mitigation from the impact of marine litter across the whole basin.

Harbours and Marinas, that are among the heavily affected areas by the effects of marine litter, could play a strategic role in the remediation and prevention process from plastic pollution in the long term. Indeed, they act as catalysts for stakeholders across the plastic value chain by favoring the connection and collaboration among the shipping and fisheries sectors, encouraging the availability and adequacy of port reception facilities, as well as the conversion of waste – such as fishing gears – into valuable materials.

Photo by Rick Katsouris on Unsplash

- “Arazzi del Mare” organized by QUANTIA – ITALIA, 24/09/2021
- Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS", 23/09/2021

#EMDinMyCountry
EMD
EUROPEAN MARITIME DAY
IN MY COUNTRY

A boost for sustainable sea and ocean solutions

Intelligent technologies for the Blue Economy – ISSS platform

23 September 2021
10:00 – 15:00 CEST

- IHOBE Comisión Basura Marina para el país vasco, 28/09/2021
https://www.ihobe.eus/agenda/urban-klima-2050-colaboracion-multisectorial-para-financiar-y-reducir-brecha-adaptacion-en-pais-vasco-2?fbclid=IwAR1eN9T4nlTIs8hUlv3hPz8jjBD4YpUe1gyKgZCzuacujWlILOzHm_448
[Q](#)

- Scienza in Villa, 01/10/2021 – 03/10/2021
<https://www.scienzainvilla.com>

- ECOMONDO 2021 - Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants, 26/10/2021
<https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/ECOMONDO%20-%20Chemical%20recycling%20-%20summary%20report%20rev%20%282%29.pdf>

<p>10:00 - 13:00 Sala Ravezzi 2 Hall Sud BLUE GROWTH Evento con la Commissione Europea</p>	<p>Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants - VERSIONE IN LINGUA INGLESE</p> <p>Lingua: inglese Traduzione simultanea: italiano</p> <p>Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee and CINEA (Sustainable Blue Economy Unit)</p> <p>The workshop will gather innovators, local and ports authorities, legislators and stakeholders, e.g. plastics association and fishers and vessels, to discuss the opportunities offered by pyrolysis plants to convert plastics waste into new chemicals. At the same time the technical and legislative barriers that hinder the exploitation of this kind of technologies will be addressed. The workshop will tackle plastics coming from different waste streams, and will specifically focus on the use of low temperature pyrolysis plants to treat marine litter.</p>
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- ECOMONDO 2021 -The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean Sea towards the 2030 targets: the strategy developed by the plastic producing and transforming operators of the area, 26/10/2021 |
<https://www.ecomondo.com/eventi/ecomondo-2022/seminari-e-convegni/e20336286/the-blued-med-pilot-healthy-plastics-free-mediterranean-sea-and-the-eu-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-by-2030.html>

Home / Eventi / Ecomondo 2022 / Programma Eventi

Ecomondo 2022

The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean sea and the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

Venerdì 11 Novembre 2022
 10:00 - 13:00
 MEMO
 Sala Diotallevi 1 Hall Sud
 Inglese

 Blue Economy

Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee & BlueMed GSOs, Federchimica-PlasticsEurope Italia, Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR), National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

- **ECOMONDO 2021 - Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean Sea, 27/10/2021**
https://en.ecomondo.com/ecomondo/programma-eventi/pdf-calendario-eventi/2021/ecomondo-2021_eng_estesa_2010.pdf

<p>14:30 - 17:30 Diotallevi 2 Room South Hall BLUE GROWTH Ecomondo Event</p>	<p>Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean - Ecomondo and Blue Sea Land Joint Event - VERSIONE IN LINGUA INGLESE</p> <p>Language: English Simultaneous translation: Italian</p> <p>Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee, Blue Sea Land, Cluster BIG, Federpesca, CNR, BLUEMED GSOs</p>
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YEAR 2022

- **Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments, 03/02/2022**
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/node/7000?fs=e&s=cl>

- EXPO Dubai: Multidisciplinary and systemic approaches for the rational use of resource and sustainability, 14/03/2022
<https://www.isoform.cnr.it/index.php/en/attivita/divulgazione/tutte-le-news/373-dubai-expo-2020-land-city-sea-scape-intelligence-multidisciplinary-and-systemic-approaches-for-the-rational-use-of-resource-and-sustainability>

- Jornadas do Mar: New Solutions for the Sustainable Removal and Management of Marine Litter, 26/03/2022 <https://www.jornadasdomar.com/schedule>

- XI Edition of the Environment Forum: “Removal and Sustainable Management of Marine Litter: Rethinking the Present, Designing the Future”, 05/04/2022

- GEOHAB 2022 – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping, 16-20/05/2022
<https://geohab.org/2022-program/>

- European Marine Robotics & Applications 2022 – Workshop, 16/06/2022
<https://noc-events.co.uk/emra-2022>

- AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS – within BIEMH22 trade fair, 17/06/2022
<https://biemh.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/en/conferences/automation-robotic-talks/>

- PLASTICA E CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI, UN MARE DA DIFENDERE, 22/06/2022
<https://www.cnr.it/it/nota-stampa/n-11193/plastico-e-cambiamenti-climatici-un-mare-da-difendere>

- UN Ocean Conference: Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event | 25/06/2022
https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/Concept%20Note%202022%20UNOC%20Local%20and%20Regional%20Gov%20Forum_REVISED_7April_for%20website%20%281%29.pdf

- UN Ocean Conference: One Sustainable Ocean–Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Event, 27/06/2022
<https://oceansciencebusiness2sea.b2match.io/>

- UN Ocean Conference: *EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action*
<https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marine-litter-monitoring-to-inform-action/>

- UN Ocean Conference: The Charter for the Mission "Restores our Ocean and Waters by 2030"
https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/charter-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2022-jun-30_en

- ERF2022 - European Robotics Forum - Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop | 28-20/06/2022
<https://erf2022.eu>

- CIIMAR open day, 18/09/2022
<https://www2.ciimar.up.pt/events.php?id=358#:~:text=On%20the%2018th%20of%20September,scientific%20activities%20with%20the%20public>

- The 7th International Marine Debris Conference is taking place this week in Busan (Republic of Korea), 18-23/12/2022
<https://internationalmarinedebrisconference.org/index.php/7imdc-home-page/>

- Marine Litter and Circular Economy workshop organized by the Interreg Italy-Croatia Programme MARELESS project, 26/11/2022
<https://programming14-20.italy-croatia.eu/web/marless>

- Black Sea CONNECT Marine Litter Action Forum, 14-15/11/2022
<http://connect2blacksea.org/marine-litter-action-forum/>

- InnovAzul 2nd International Meeting on Knowledge and the Blue Economy - Open Innovation Session, 29 November 2022
<https://aquabt.com/event/innovazul-2nd-international-meeting-on-knowledge-and-the-blue-economy/>

- Webinar "Pan-European digital assets supporting research communities – Benefits & Opportunities", 5-6/12/2022
<https://eoscfuture.eu/eventsfuture/webinar-pan-european-digital-assets-supporting-research-communities-benefits-opportunities/>

Experiences from Early Adopters approaching EOSC: the RELIANCE Open challenge for sustainable development for sustainable development

- Kick Off Meeting Horizon CSA BluemissionMed project, 27/01/2023 <https://bluemissionmed.eu/>

- EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters 1st Annual Forum, 17/02/2023 <https://icfnext.swoogo.com/MissionForum2023>

- AI for Good Webinar: Sustainable robots: What does it take for a robot to be sustainable?, 28/02/2023
<https://aiforgood.itu.int/event/sustainable-robots-what-does-it-take-for-a-robot-to-be-sustainable/>

- Advancing the Un Sustainable Development Goals with Autonomous Robots - as part of the 14th European Robotics Forum 2023, 14-16/03/2023
<https://erf2023.sdu.dk/.../phd-award-finalists-pitches-2/>

- CINEA Workshop Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects, 17/04/2023
https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/events/workshop-ocean-health-observation-2023-04-17_en

EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA)

CINEA.D - Natural resources, climate, sustainable blue economy and clean energy
D.3 - Sustainable Blue Economy

**Synergies and Clustering between Maritime Projects
(EASME/EMFF/2020/3.1.12) – SI2.850620**

“Workshop on Ocean Health & Observation”

- GEOHAB 2023, 5-12/05/2023
<https://geohab.org/geohab-2023/>

GEOHAB
Marine Geological and Biological Habitat Mapping
International Symposium 2023
May 8-12 th - Reunion Island

- Antropocene Exhibition (Venice), 6/05/2023
<https://antropocene.cnr.it/>

- European Maritime Day, 24-25/05
<https://european-maritime-day-2023.b2match.io/?fbclid=IwAR15T6iNZBh4SQWpkowsR2WBnewnwEdLIA&y-leYSY67quM2Ove8AnDXiDY>

- EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters – The Mediterranean Lighthouse in Action, 30/05 – 01/06

https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-by-2030-the-mediterranean-lighthouse-in-action/?fbclid=IwAR1Tu_TknAJnr0Uhs1FTpFGwUmLPs6t6AOqg-oeqJHnBS4xLqqw_dG1jiQ

- 2013 – 2023: 10 years of the Galway Statement, 5-6/07/2023
<https://allatlanticocean.org/events/10-years-of-the-galway-statement/>

- Ciência Viva - Science and Ocean Beyond the Horizon, Aveiro, 5/07/2023
<https://www.encontrociencia.pt/2023/pt>

- CIIMAR Open Day, 17/09/2023
<https://www2.ciimar.up.pt/events.php?id=447>

- Portuguese Third Conference on Marine Litter and Microplastics, 21-22/09/2023
<https://aplixomarinho.org/3cplm/>

#3CPLM #LIXOMARINHO #APLIXOMARINHO
#MICROPLASTICOS #PAVILHAODOCONHECIMENTO

**10 ANOS
POR UM MAR SEM LIXO**

21 > 22 SETEMBRO 2023
PAVILHÃO DO CONHECIMENTO

- Scienza in Villa, 23/09/2023
<https://www.memorialegrandequerra.it/>

- Ocean Best Practices (OBPS) Workshop VII - Challenge 1 – Understand and beat marine pollution, 17/10/2023

<https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/community-engagement/workshops/ocean-practices-obps-workshop-vii-09-13-oct-2023-online/ocean-practices-obps-workshop-vii-registration-and->

[agenda/#:~:text=The%20OBPS%20Workshop%20VII%2C%202023,Decade%20Actions%20and%20Programmes%20participation](#)

- 10th Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference - All Atlantic Award, 18-19/10/2023
<https://atlantic-maritime-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news-and-events/events/atlantic-stakeholder-platform-conference-2023>

- TREC - Traversing European Coastlines Expedition, 26/11/2023
<https://www.embl.org/about/info/trec/expedition/>

- ECOMONDO, 7-10/11/2023
<https://www.ecomondo.com/>

- UNEP INC-3 (Plastic Treaty), 13-19/11/2023
<https://www.unep.org/inc-plastic-pollution/session-3>

- Conference on the Protection of Waters and Seas from Plastics and Micro-plastics Pollution, 29/11/2023
<https://www.adriatic-ionian.eu/conference-on-the-protection-of-waters-and-seas-from-plastics-and-micro-plastics-pollution/>

